

POLITECNICO DI MILANO
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Civile e Ambientale

POLITECNICO
MILANO 1863

**ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF
IRRIGATION ON PO RIVER
HYDROLOGIC REGIME**

Relatore: Prof. Giovanni Ravazzani

Tesi di laurea di:
Daniele Sala Matr. 996440

Anno accademico 2023/2024

Acknowledgements

Vorrei esprimere la mia sincera gratitudine al Politecnico di Milano, al Dipartimento di Ingegneria Civile e Ambientale, e in particolar modo al Professor Giovanni Ravazzani. La vostra guida, supporto e l'opportunità fornita sono stati inestimabili durante il lungo percorso di questo progetto di tesi. Il Politecnico di Milano mi ha anche dato la possibilità di incontrare tante persone meravigliose, con vite e percorsi completamente diversi dal mio, che non avrei mai incontrato se l'università non fosse anche un luogo splendido per la socializzazione e la connessione, oltre che un luogo di studio.

Un sentito ringraziamento a tutti i membri della 4B. Studiare può essere impegnativo, ma avere le persone giuste intorno fa tutta la differenza. Non avrei potuto chiedere compagni migliori durante questo periodo.

Un ringraziamento speciale ad Alice. Durante gran parte di questo viaggio, sia negli studi che nella vita, sei stata una fonte costante di supporto e ispirazione. La tua incrollabile fiducia in me, anche nei momenti più difficili, è stata inestimabile. Anche se le nostre vite hanno preso strade diverse, l'impatto che hai avuto sulla mia crescita accademica e personale è qualcosa che custodirò sempre. Spero di essere riuscito a fornirti lo stesso livello di supporto, e sono grato per i ricordi e la forza che abbiamo condiviso.

A Bana e Fillo, il nostro viaggio insieme è iniziato all'asilo e continua quasi 20 anni dopo. Dai nostri primi giorni di scuola a questo importante traguardo, la nostra amicizia è stata una costante fonte di motivazione e gioia. Le innumerevoli giornate trascorse assieme hanno formato la persona che sono oggi. Ora, mentre le circostanze cambiano e il tempo insieme diventa sempre meno, la vostra importanza nella mia vita rimane immutata.

Sono profondamente grato alla mia famiglia per il loro costante supporto durante il mio percorso accademico. Il vostro incoraggiamento e la vostra fiducia in me sono stati i miei pilastri di forza.

Un pensiero speciale va a te, nonna, che ci sei stata fin da quando ero piccolo e che tenevi tantissimo ad esserci in questo momento di gioia. Sfortunatamente non è potuto essere così, ma un ringraziamento speciale va soprattutto a te.

Grazie a tutti per il vostro contributo per questo grande traguardo raggiunto.

Summary

This thesis examines the impact of agricultural irrigation on the hydrologic regime of the Po River Basin using the FEST (Flash Flood Event-based Simulation Technique) hydrological model. It begins with an overview of the Po River Basin, including its meteorological and soil parameters, highlighting the significance of efficient water resource management in agriculture, particularly within this region which significantly contributes to Italy's GDP and agricultural output.

The study identifies and analyzes irrigation districts, focusing on the roles of various reclamation and irrigation consortia. Major water diversions and their impacts on the regional water balance are detailed, providing a foundation for subsequent sensitivity analysis.

A comprehensive sensitivity analysis explores key parameters influencing water flow and aquifer interactions, such as deep percolation factors, SCS Curve Number, and hydraulic conductivity. These analyses are essential for understanding the hydrological dynamics and for calibrating the FEST model to enhance its predictive accuracy.

Calibration and validation of the FEST model are conducted using historical data from 2011 to 2020, demonstrating the model's reliability in simulating river discharges and cumulative water volumes. The validation highlights the model's ability to capture the hydrological response to irrigation practices, focusing on river flow rates, evapotranspiration, and aquifer levels.

A significant part of the thesis investigates scenarios without agricultural irrigation, revealing increased river flows, reduced evapotranspiration, and higher aquifer levels, especially during dry months. These findings underscore the substantial influence of irrigation on the hydrological cycle.

The research also considers future developments, including varying irrigation windows and modifying water allocation rates. Additionally, it suggests analyzing the impacts of changing water concession systems for irrigation during particularly dry years, such as 2022. These adjustments aim to optimize water usage and ensure the sustainability of water resources in the region.

Table of Contents

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF IRRIGATION ON PO RIVER HYDROLOGIC REGIME	I
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	III
SUMMARY	V
TABLE OF FIGURES	IX
TABLE OF TABLES	XI
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION	1
CHAPTER 2 THE PO RIVER BASIN CASE STUDY.....	3
2.1 METEOROLOGICAL DATA OF PO RIVER BASIN.....	3
2.2 SOIL RELATED PARAMETERS OF PO RIVER BASIN.....	6
2.3 WATER CONTENT AT SATURATION	7
2.4 RESIDUAL WATER CONTENT.....	9
2.5 LAMBDA.....	13
2.6 SATURATED HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY.....	15
2.7 WATER CONTENT FIELD CAPACITY	17
2.8 WATER CONTENT AT WILTING POINT.....	19
CHAPTER 3 DEVELOPMENT OF NEW FEST MODULES	23
3.1 STREAM-GROUNDWATER INTERACTION	23
3.2 FEST MODEL SCHEME.....	25
CHAPTER 4 IDENTIFICATION OF IRRIGATION DISTRICT.....	27
4.1 MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: RECLAMATION AND IRRIGATION CONSORTIA.....	27
4.1.1 Consortia in the Po River Basin.....	28
4.2 IDENTIFICATION OF MAJOR DERIVATIONS	29
4.2.1 Po River.....	30
4.2.2 Sesia River	30
4.2.3 Ticino River.....	31
4.2.4 Adda River	32
4.2.5 Oglio River	34
4.2.6 Serio River	35

4.2.7 Chiese River	36
4.2.8 Mincio River.....	37
4.3 IDENTIFICATION OF AREAS IRRIGATED BY EACH DERIVATION.....	37
CHAPTER 5 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS	41
5.1 DEEP PERCOLATION FACTOR	42
5.1.1 Results and comments	44
5.2 SCS CURVE NUMBER	45
5.2.1 Results and comments.....	47
5.3 HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY	51
5.3.1 Results and comments.....	51
5.4 INTERACTION RIVER-AQUIFER.....	55
5.4.1 Results and comments.....	56
5.5 CHANNEL ROUTING.....	60
5.5.1 Results and comments.....	62
CHAPTER 6 FEST CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION	65
6.1 CALIBRATION.....	66
6.2 VALIDATION	69
CHAPTER 7 EXPLORING IRRIGATION SCENARIOS.....	73
7.1 COMPARISON WITH NO IRRIGATION SIMULATION	74
7.2 FUTURE DEVELOPMENT	78
CHAPTER 8 CONCLUSIONS	79
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	81

Table of figures

Figure 2.1 The 21km spatial resolution MERIDA analysis domain (grey) with the internal grid centered on Italy at 7km spatial resolution.	4
Figure 2.2 Comparison of ERA5 and MERIDA data: Annual precipitation and Temperature (1990-2020)	4
Figure 2.3 Map of cross sections of the Po River of the available discharge data.	5
Figure 2.4 Average daily Po River discharge for the period 1990-2020.	6
Figure 2.5 Map of water content at saturation.	9
Figure 2.6 Map of residual water content.	13
Figure 2.7 Map of Brooks and Corey pore size distribution index.	15
Figure 2.8 Map of soil hydraulic conductivity at saturation (m/s)	17
Figure 2.9 Map of soil water content at field capacity.	19
Figure 2.10 Map of soil water content at wilting point.	21
Figure 3.1 Map of the aquifer simulation domain (grey), Dirichlet type boundary condition cells (red) and Neumann type boundary condition cells (yellow)	24
Figure 3.2 Scheme of hydrological processes implemented within FeST model with main state variables and input data.	26
Figure 4.1 Map representing the 21 more extended irrigated areas	39
Figure 5.1 Soil balance scheme of cell on hillslope(up) and of a cell on land plain (down) RZD = root zone depth, TZD = transmission zone depth, I = infiltration, ET = evapotranspiration, RSE = saturation excess from root zone, P = percolation, TSE = saturation excess from transmission zone, LF _{IN} =input lateral flux, LF _{OUT} = output lateral flux, DP = deep percolation.	43
Figure 5.2 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of deep percolation factor.	45
Figure 5.3 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of CN offset.	49
Figure 5.4 Simulated discharge with different offset values in 2014.	50
Figure 5.5 Cumulated volumes with different offset values in the calibration period 2011-2015.	50

Figure 5.6 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of Permeability scale factor.	53
Figure 5.7 Simulated discharge with different scale factor values in 2014.	54
Figure 5.8 Cumulative volumes with different scale factor values in the calibration period 2011-2015.	54
Figure 5.9 Conceptual representation of river-aquifer interconnection: Q is the discharge, L is the stream length, W is the stream width, M is the streambed thickness, hw is the hydraulic head in the stream, and h is the hydraulic head in the aquifer.	56
Figure 5.10 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of river-aquifer conductivity.	58
Figure 5.11 Simulated discharge with different conductivity values in 2014.	59
Figure 5.12 Cumulative volumes with different conductivity values in the calibration period 2011-2015.	59
Figure 5.13 Head aquifer with different conductivity values in the calibration period 2011-2015.	60
Figure 5.14 Simulated and observed discharge with different configurations in the 2011 annual peak period.	64
Figure 6.1 Simulated discharge with the final set of parameters in 2014.	67
Figure 6.2 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the calibration period 2011-2015.	68
Figure 6.3 Waterflow cyclostationary observed and simulated mean in Pontelagoscuro during the calibration period 2011-2015.	69
Figure 6.4 Simulated discharge with the final set of parameters in 2017.	70
Figure 6.5 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the validation period 2011-2020.	71
Figure 6.6 Waterflow cyclostationary observed and simulated mean in Pontelagoscuro during the validation period 2011-2020.	71
Figure 7.1 Waterflow cyclostationary simulated means with and without irrigation in Pontelagoscuro during the validation period 2011-2020.	75
Figure 7.2 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the validation period 2011-2020.	76
Figure 7.3 Evapotranspiration cyclostationary simulated means with and without irrigation during the validation period 2011-2020.	76
Figure 7.4 Head of aquifer compared with the cumulated discharge volume of the irrigation.	77

Table of tables

Table 2.1 Location of different sections of Po River considered for the simulations.	5
Table 2.2 Required input data for Pedotransfer function.	6
Table 2.3 Ranges of variability of saturated hydraulic conductivity (mm/h)	17
Table 4.1 Results of the calculation method for the irrigated areas by each diversion in comparison with literature data.	38
Table 5.1 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station	44
Table 5.2 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station	44
Table 5.3 Aggregated value for the evaluation of deep percolation factor effect on the waterflow	44
Table 5.4 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with offset = -10	47
Table 5.5 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with offset = -10	48
Table 5.6 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with offset = +10	48
Table 5.7 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with offset = +10	48
Table 5.8 Aggregated value for the evaluation of CN variations effect on the waterflow in comparison between the four simulations.	48
Table 5.9 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 0.01	52
Table 5.10 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 0.01	52
Table 5.11 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 10	52
Table 5.12 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 10	52

Table 5.13 Aggregated value for the evaluation of conductivity variations effect on the waterflow in comparison between the three simulations	53
Table 5.14 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with a river-aquifer conductivity of 10^{-6}	57
Table 5.15 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with a river-aquifer conductivity of 10^{-6}	57
Table 5.16 Aggregated value for the evaluation of river-aquifer conductivity effect on the waterflow in comparison between the three simulations.	57
Table 5.17 Properties of the hydrological channel	63
Table 6.1 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters	66
Table 6.2 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume, NMRSE and NSE for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters	66
Table 6.3 Aggregated value for the simulation with the final set of parameters and the standard simulation	67
Table 6.4 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the period 2016-2020	69
Table 6.5 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume, NMRSE and NSE for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the validation period 2011-2020	70
Table 6.6 Aggregated value for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the calibration and validation period	70
Table 7.1 New location of different sections of Po River considered for the comparison.	73
Table 7.2 Aggregated value for the final simulation with and without irrigation in the validation period 2011-2020.	74
Table 7.3 Annual $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume between the simulations with and without the irrigation	74
Table 7.4 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume during the irrigation period between the simulations with and without the irrigation	75

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The practice of irrigation in Italy has a rich historical backdrop deeply entrenched in ancient traditions. It finds its roots in the management of water resources, an endeavor that has been crucial for agricultural sustenance throughout history. Approximately 75% of irrigated areas in Europe are concentrated in countries like Greece, Italy, Portugal, and Spain (EU-27), attesting to the significance of irrigation in sustaining agricultural productivity across the continent. Italy has a longstanding legacy in water resource management, dating back to significant historical milestones.

The year 1179 marked a pivotal moment with the construction of the first canal diverting water for irrigation purposes, exemplified by the grand canal connecting Milan to Lake Maggiore. Subsequent advancements in 1225 led to the establishment of the "Muzza" and "Fozza di Pazzolo" channels, further solidifying Italy's commitment to efficient water distribution for agricultural needs. These historical endeavors laid the groundwork for the intricate network of water management systems that persist today (Gandolfi, 2017).

The management of irrigation in Italy is overseen by consortiums, which play a vital role in regulating water distribution and usage. In 2009-2010, these consortiums utilized approximately 11.618 million cubic meters of water for irrigation, highlighting the scale of water resources involved in sustaining agricultural practices across the country (Gandolfi, 2017).

However, despite this rich history and infrastructure, contemporary irrigation management faces significant challenges, particularly in regions like Lombardia in northern Italy. Here, approximately 62% of irrigation relies on low-efficiency techniques such as surface irrigation, leading to considerable water wastage (Gandolfi, 2017). The rigidity within the existing water delivery systems, characterized by fixed irrigation schedules set by consortiums, often compels farmers to over-irrigate whenever water is available, exacerbating issues of water scarcity and

inefficiency. These practices not only lead to detrimental impacts on crop health, such as oxygen deprivation and leaching of fertilizers but also contribute to overall water losses within the system (Gandolfi, 2017).

The urgency to address these challenges is further compounded by the escalating impacts of climate change, which pose unprecedented threats to agricultural sustainability and water resource management. As highlighted in various studies (IPCC, 2007; Stzeppek et al., 2011; Fisheha et al., 2014; Senatore et al., 2011; Ravazzani et al., 2015), climate change is expected to exacerbate water scarcity, particularly in regions like the Po River basin in northern Italy. Historically characterized by water abundance, the Po River basin has been a cornerstone of agricultural development, covering a significant portion of the region's agricultural lands. Spanning approximately 74,000 km², with 141 main tributaries and a total river network length of about 6750 km, the Po River basin constitutes a vital economic and ecological entity within Italy (Po River Basin Authority, 2006; Montanari, 2012). Economically, this river basin constitutes 40% of Italian GDP and 35% of national agricultural production (Po River Basin Authority, 2006).

In addition to its economic significance, the Po River basin has been extensively studied in the context of hydrological modeling. Various distributed hydrological models, such as the CATHY model (Camporese et al., 2010), SWAT model (Arnold et al., 1993) integrated with MODFLOW (McDonald and Harbaugh, 1988), mike-she model (Graham and Butts, 2005), FEST-WB (Ravazzani et al., 2015), and WaSiM-eth model (Shulla and Jasper, 2007), have been developed and utilized to understand its complex hydrological behavior and responses to external factors like climate change.

Considering these challenges and the existing body of research, this thesis aims to employ sophisticated hydrological modeling, specifically the FEST model, to analyze and propose new scenarios for irrigation management within the Po River basin. By integrating insights from existing literature and leveraging advanced modeling techniques, this research seeks to develop enhanced strategies for sustainable water resource management in the face of evolving climatic conditions. By doing so, it aspires to contribute to the broader discourse on adaptive water management practices in agrarian landscapes, particularly in regions vulnerable to the impacts of climate change.

CHAPTER 2

THE PO RIVER BASIN CASE STUDY

The Po River, renowned as the longest river flowing exclusively within the Italian peninsula, drains a vast basin covering approximately 74,000 km² in surface area, with about 71,000 km² located within Italian borders. The primary objective of the simulations conducted in this research is to analyze the effects of various irrigation scenarios on the hydrological behavior of the Po River basin.

2.1 Meteorological data of Po River Basin

Two data sources for historical meteorological data were found for our study area which are: ERA 5 and MERIDA.

ERA5 provides estimates of atmospheric variables such as air temperature, pressure, wind, humidity and ozone at different altitudes, surface variables such as rainfall, soil moisture, sea-surface temperature, all at a spatial resolution of about 31 km worldwide. ERA5-Land provides hourly high-resolution information of surface variables. The data is a replay of the land component of the ERA5 climate reanalysis with a finer spatial resolution: ~9km grid spacing. The MEteorological Reanalysis Italian DATaset (MERIDA) has been developed to deal with the increasingly frequent extreme weather conditions of the last 20 years, which have caused several disruptions to the Italian electricity system. MERIDA consists of a dynamic downscaling of the ERA5 global reanalysis using the WRF-ARW limited area model. ERA5 data is assimilated with a 3-hour time resolution to ensure good temporal consistency. Even the temperature data of the Air Force SYNOP stations are assimilated in WRF simulations with a time resolution of 3 hours. The MERIDA domain consists of 2 grids with a horizontal resolution of 21 km and 7 km respectively, with the internal grid centered on Italy (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 The 21km spatial resolution MERIDA analysis domain (grey) with the internal grid centered on Italy at 7km spatial resolution.

Figure 2.2 Comparison of ERA5 and MERIDA data: Annual precipitation and Temperature (1990-2020)

After a comparison between the ERA5-Land and MERIDA datasets in the period 1990-2020, which showed minimal differences between the two datasets (as shown in Figure 2.1), the decision was made to use the MERIDA dataset.

Hydrological data at daily time resolution have been downloaded from the ARPA Emilia-Romagna region web site. For this project we selected 6 different sections (reported in the table 2.1 below), with Pontelagoscuro as the closure of the Po River basin.

Table 2.1 Location of different sections of Po River considered for the simulations.

SECTION	DISTRICT	REGION	ELEVATION	LONG.	LAT.-
Spessa Po	Arena Po	Lombardia	64	9.3460	45.1017
Piacenza	Piacenza	Emilia-Romagna	55	9.7055	45.0605
Cremona	Cremona	Lombardia	45	9.9948	45.1283
Boretto	Boretto	Emilia-Romagna	30	10.5589	44.9063
Borgoforte	Borgoforte	Lombardia	29	10.7591	45.0456
Pontelagoscuro	Ferrara	Emilia-Romagna	8	11.6080	44.8883

Figure 2.3 Map of cross sections of the Po River of the available discharge data.

The figure 2.4 below reports the average daily river discharge of last 10 years of observed data. Discharges of Po River are characterized by two maxima, in spring and autumn, and two minima, in winter and summer.

Figure 2.4 Average daily Po River discharge for the period 1990-2020.

2.2 Soil related parameters of Po River Basin

Soil parameters are required input data in order to carry out the hydrological simulations. Considering the large area of the river basin, it was not possible to get enough measured soil parameters. As an alternative, we decided to proceed with the estimation of the soil parameters using Pedotransfer equations developed for the Po River basin. The PTFs were developed using a group method of data handling (GMDH) technique. These equations allow to estimate soil hydraulic parameters based on readily available soil parameters such as: soil texture, % of clay, % of sand, % of loam, bulk density, organic matter content of the soil. These Pedotransfer functions were elaborated by (Ungaro, et al., 2005), for this particular area, so there was no need to calibrate them. Required inputs to estimate the soil hydraulic parameters using these Pedotransfer functions are reported in the Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Required input data for Pedotransfer function.

PARAMETER	FORMULA
S%	%sand
L%	%silt
A%	%clay
CO%	% of organic carbon

BD MGM-3	Bulk density
A	$0.01 * (\%A * ((\text{LN}(2) + \text{LN}(0.05))/2) + \%L * ((\text{LN}(0.002) + \text{LN}(0.05))/2) + \%S * ((\text{LN}(0.00004) + \text{LN}(0.002))/2))$
B	$0.01 * (\%S * (((\text{LN}(2) + \text{LN}(0.05))/2)) ^2 + \%L * (((\text{LN}(0.002) + \text{LN}(0.05))/2)) ^2 + \%A * (((\text{LN}(0.00004) + \text{LN}(0.002))/2)) ^2) - A^2)^{0.5}$
DG	Exp(a)
SG	Exp(b)
LNCS1	$\text{LN}(\%A / (\%A + \%L))$
S%	$\text{LN}(\%A / (\%A + \%L)) / \text{LN}(2/50)$
PORO1	$(1 - (\text{BD} / (2.7 * (1 - (\text{CO} \% * 10^{-2}) + \text{CO} \% * 10^{-2})))) * 0.96$
PORO2	$1 - (\text{BD} / 2.65)$

2.3 Water content at saturation

Saturated water content θ_s is the maximum amount of water a soil can store. This parameter is estimated using the following equations.

$$X_1 = -0.92542 + (0.00101 \times (A\%)^2) \quad \text{Eq. (2.1)}$$

$$X_2 = -0.48534 + (0.36518 \times CO) \quad \text{Eq. (2.2)}$$

$$X_3 = -3.88463 + (1.87110 \times (BD)^2) \quad \text{Eq. (2.3)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 out_1 = & -0.387803561 + (0.11847111 \times X_1) & \text{Eq.(2.4)} \\
 & + (-0.699691202 \times X_2) \\
 & + (-0.387613179 \times X_3) \\
 & + (0.4573358 \times X_1^2) + (0.96013265 \times X_2^2) \\
 & + (0 \times X_3^2) + (-0.471708638 \times X_1 \times X_2) \\
 & + (0.076771834 \times X_1 \times X_3) \\
 & + (0.437276314 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\
 & + (-0.041557322 \times X_1 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\
 & + (-0.117925553 \times X_1^3) \\
 & + (-0.294756534 \times X_2^3) \\
 & + (0.137207593 \times X_3^3) \\
 & + (0.616727307 \times X_1^2 \times X_2) \\
 & + (-0.28507601 \times X_2^2 \times X_1) \\
 & + (0.039445579 \times X_3^2 \times X_1) \\
 & + (0.145852004 \times X_1^2 \times X_3) \\
 & + (-0.064699387 \times X_2^2 \times X_3) \\
 & + (0.56445016 \times X_3^2 \times X_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta_s^* = 0.434952381 + (0.07215499 \times out_1) \quad \text{Eq.(2.5)}$$

If

$$\theta_s^* > 0.88 \text{ Then } \theta_s = 0.88 \quad \text{Eq.(2.6)}$$

If

$$\theta_s^* < 0.18 \text{ Then } \theta_s = 0.18 \quad \text{Eq.(2.7)}$$

Otherwise

$$\theta_s = \theta_s^* \quad \text{Eq.(2.8)}$$

Figure 2.5 Map of water content at saturation.

2.4 Residual water content

The residual water content θ_R is usually considered as the minimum soil moisture, at which its corresponding matric suction is infinite. This parameter is calculated using the formulas below.

$$X_1 = -0.93012 + (0.00102 \times (A\%)^2) \quad \text{Eq. (2.9)}$$

$$X_2 = -3.87314 + (1.87339 \times (BD)^2) \quad \text{Eq.(2.10)}$$

$$X_3 = -5.57031 + (12.01056 \times Poro2) \quad \text{Eq.(2.11)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
out_1 = & -3.01330082 + (-3.482895596 \times X_1) && \text{Eq.(2.12)} \\
& + (-29.38668062 \times X_2) \\
& + (-36.84182916 \times X_3) \\
& + (0.193544184 \times X_1^2) \\
& + (15.30049571 \times X_2^2) \\
& + (-10.56962086 \times X_3^2) \\
& + (-41.43004541 \times X_1 \times X_2) \\
& + (-48.70004553 \times X_1 \times X_3) \\
& + (6.341342373 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\
& + (17.51189458 \times X_1 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\
& + (-0.095908357 \times X_1^3) \\
& + (-26.23836309 \times X_2^3) \\
& + (-16.92639419 \times X_3^3) \\
& + (-1.249366407 \times X_1^2 \times X_2) \\
& + (7.343829632 \times X_2^2 \times X_1) \\
& + (14.08348268 \times X_3^2 \times X_1) \\
& + (-1.489007654 \times X_1^2 \times X_3) \\
& + (-71.69704694 \times X_2^2 \times X_3) \\
& + (-64.71322387 \times X_3^2 \times X_2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$Y_2 = -1.24194 + (0.046304344 \times (S\%)^2) \quad \text{Eq.(2.13)}$$

$$Y_3 = -7.584022891 + (3.392217545 \times \ln (sg)) \quad \text{Eq.(2.14)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 out_2 = & 0.151820745 + (1.367619369 \times out_1) + (0 \times Y_2) & \text{Eq.(2.15)} \\
 & + (0.100242199 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (0.118915866 \times out_1^2) \\
 & + (-0.108658122 \times Y_2^2) + (0 \times Y_3^2) \\
 & + (0 \times out_1 \times Y_2) \\
 & + (0.187587623 \times out_1 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (-0.196040735 \times Y_2 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (-0.549576088 \times out_1 \times Y_2 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (0 \times out_1^3) + (0 \times Y_2^3) \\
 & + (-0.050980173 \times Y_3^3) \\
 & + (0.04619216 \times out_1^2 \times Y_2) \\
 & + (-0.251868272 \times Y_2^2 \times out_1) \\
 & + (0 \times Y_3^2 \times out_1) \\
 & + (0.114256341 \times out_1^2 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (0.046616775 \times Y_2^2 \times Y_3) \\
 & + (0 \times Y_3^2 \times Y_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$Z_2 = -2.903947414 + (0.9511152 \times (BD)^3) \quad \text{Eq.(2.16)}$$

$$Z_3 = -0.981679952 + (0.0446884198 \times 1) \quad \text{Eq.(2.17)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 out_3 = & -0.098823409 + (0.778315385 \times out_2) & \text{Eq.(2.18)} \\
 & + (0 \times Z_2) + (-0.199776504 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (0.642744774 \times out_2^2) \\
 & + (0.048546298 \times Z_2^2) \\
 & + (0.063495887 \times Z_3^2) \\
 & + (0.598505219 \times out_2 \times Z_2) \\
 & + (0 \times out_2 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (0.232607153 \times Z_2 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (0 \times out_2 \times Z_2 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (-0.221921736 \times out_2^3) \\
 & + (0.124130409 \times Z_2^3) + (0 \times Z_3^3) \\
 & + (-0.355862674 \times out_2^2 \times Z_2) \\
 & + (0.082821193 \times Z_2^2 \times out_2) \\
 & + (0.116290436 \times Z_3^2 \times out_2) \\
 & + (0.278094543 \times out_2^2 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (0.047810852 \times Z_2^2 \times Z_3) \\
 & + (-0.093065282 \times Z_3^2 \times Z_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta_r^* = 0.050176471 + (0.099876247 \times out_3) \quad \text{Eq.(2.19)}$$

If

$$\theta_r^* > 0.531 \text{ then } \theta_r = 0.531 \quad \text{Eq.(2.20)}$$

If

$$\theta_r^* < 0 \text{ then } \theta_r = 0 \quad \text{Eq.(2.21)}$$

Otherwise

$$\theta_r = \theta_r^* \quad \text{Eq.(2.22)}$$

Figure 2.6 Map of residual water content.

2.5 Lambda

Lambda is defined as Brooks and Corey pore size distribution index. This parameter is estimated using the formulas reported below.

$$X_1 = -0.62012 + (28.71818 \times Dg) \quad \text{Eq.(2.23)}$$

$$X_2 = -6.42106 + (4.51727 \times BD) \quad \text{Eq.(2.24)}$$

$$X_3 = -0.97762 + (0.04454 \times 1) \quad \text{Eq.(2.25)}$$

$$out_1 = 0 + (0.747242989 \times X_1) + (0 \times X_2) \quad \text{Eq.(2.26)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ (-0.123851523 \times X_3) \\ &+ (-0.434956376 \times X_1^2) \\ &+ (-0.225398144 \times X_2^2) \\ &+ (0.400397351 \times X_3^2) \\ &+ (-0.231104356 \times X_1 \times X_2) \\ &+ (-0.281896772 \times X_1 \times X_3) + (0 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\ &+ (-0.34777617 \times X_1 \times X_2 \times X_3) \\ &+ (0.065327512 \times X_1^3) \\ &+ (-0.095393516 \times X_2^3) \\ &+ (-0.084383313 \times X_3^3) \\ &+ (0.130799394 \times X_1^2 \times X_2) \\ &+ (-0.109404557 \times X_2^2 \times X_1) \\ &+ (0.187929106 \times X_3^2 \times X_1) \\ &+ (-0.056976403 \times X_1^2 \times X_3) \\ &+ (0.045501344 \times X_2^2 \times X_3) \\ &+ (-0.087762832 \times X_3^2 \times X_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$Y_2 = -2.570481625 + (7.101887963 \times lncs2) \quad \text{Eq.(2.26)}$$

$$Outd_1 = -0.153807588 + (0.844084375 \times out_1) \quad \text{Eq.(2.27)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ (0 \times Y_2) + (0.157575062 \times out_1^2) \\ &+ (0.088403822 \times Y_2^2) + (0 \times out_1 \times Y_2) \\ &+ (-0.02636365 \times out_1^3) + (0 \times Y_2^3) \\ &+ (0 \times out_1^2 \times Y_2) + (0 \times Y_2^2 \times Xout_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$Lambda^* = 0.165789474 + (0.156895951 \times outd1) \quad \text{Eq.(2.28)}$$

If

$$Lambda^* > 0.927 \text{ then } Lambda = 0.927 \quad \text{Eq.(2.29)}$$

If

$$\text{Lambda}^* < 0.04 \text{ then } \text{Lambda} = 0.04 \quad \text{Eq.(2.30)}$$

Otherwise

$$\text{Lambda} = \text{Lambda}^* \quad \text{Eq.(2.31)}$$

Figure 2.7 Map of Brooks and Corey pore size distribution index.

2.6 Saturated hydraulic conductivity

Saturated hydraulic conductivity, K_{SAT} , describes water movement through a saturated soil. The formulas used for the calculation of this parameter are the following. (Convert K_{SAT} calculated here in mm/h should be converted to m/s)

$$A = -1.58807939026797 + 0.043399261792585 \times S\% \quad \text{Eq.(2.32)}$$

$$B = 0.895704956226224 \quad \text{Eq.(2.33)}$$

$$+ 1.90436429623194 \times \log(CO\%)$$

$$C = -6.56853764508901 + 4.86964821073382 * BD \quad \text{Eq.(2.34)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D = & 0.0836015967122676 + 0.416153421876942 \times A & \text{Eq.(2.35)} \\
& + 0 \times B + -0.445772230372808 \times C \\
& + -0.134334562427775 \times A^2 \\
& + -0.0544032825090131 \times B^2 \\
& + 0 \times C^2 \\
& + -0.198584356240143 \times A \times B \\
& + 0.096017083549925 \times A \times C \\
& + -0.144971973570487 \times B \times C + - \\
& -0.125314845712128 \times A \times B \times C \\
& + 0.0716205065345566 \times A^3 \\
& + -0.123673920290893 \times B^3 \\
& + 0.0587033757513834 \times C^3 \\
& + 0.152071065904968 \times A^2 \times B \\
& + -0.102414907323155 \times A \times B^2 \\
& + 0 \times A \times C^2 + 0 \times A^2 \times C \\
& + -0.156148957009503 \times B^2 \times C \\
& + -0.0305947339564729 \times B \times C^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$E = -1.65784483580252 + 0.0723996897397788 \times A\% \quad \text{Eq.(2.36)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F = & 0.174732633027132 + 1.03829358346795 \times D & \text{Eq.(2.37)} \\
& + 0.151865200913679 \times E \\
& + -0.341867233805586 \times D^2 \\
& + -0.11074767165566 \times E^2 \\
& + -0.13351716106058 \times D \times E \\
& + -0.461153694809156 \times D^3 + 0 \times E^3 \\
& + -0.367403924274197 \times D^2 \times E \\
& + -0.218709934220076 \times D \times E^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Log Ksat} = & 0.951757462686567 & \text{Eq.(2.38)} \\
& + 1.10472133391165 \times F
\end{aligned}$$

$$K_{\text{sat}} = 10^{\text{LogKsat}} \quad \text{Eq.(2.39)}$$

(Ksat calculated here in mm/h should be converted to m/s)

Table 2.3 Ranges of variability of saturated hydraulic conductivity (mm/h)

SOIL TEXTURE	MIN	MAX
FINE	1.222×10^{-9}	0.0000067611
MEDIUM	$2.583333333 \times 10^{-7}$	0.0000280361
COARSE	0.0000020944	0.0001116083

2.7 Water content field capacity

Field capacity CI_{333} is the water content of a soil after gravitational drainage has completed. The suction that defines this value varies from soil-to-soil ranges usually between 10–33 kPa. This parameter is important for the determination of the available water content for plant extraction. The water content at field capacity is calculated as follows.

$$A = -1.58807939026797 + 0.043399261792585 \times S\% \quad \text{Eq.(2.40)}$$

$$B = -0.491141860677084 \quad \text{Eq.(2.41)}$$

$$+ 0.367776345566818 \times Corg\%$$

$$C = -5.88752433612624 \quad \text{Eq.(2.42)}$$

$$+ 13.0483582639121 \times POR01$$

$$\begin{aligned}
D = & 0 + -0.47522648155494 \times A && \text{Eq.(2.43)} \\
& + 0.407409693528406 \times B \\
& + 0.101954382069889 \times C + 0 * A^2 \\
& + 0.286127938068712 \times B^2 \\
& + -0.103499406792212 \times C^2 \\
& + 0 \times A \times B \\
& + 0.164039073693382 \times A \times C \\
& + 0.385057943571155 \times B \times C \\
& + 0.302594161247526 \times A \times B \times C \\
& + -0.118517243948488 \times A^3 \\
& + -0.00799822709229998 \times B^3 \\
& + -0.0474755798398775 \times C^3 \\
& - 0.259973976218855 \times A^2 \times B \\
& + 0.0279859549205733 \times A * B^2 \\
& + -0.0932679649932655 * A \times C^2 \\
& + 0 \times A^2 * C \\
& + -0.307603329158264 \times B^2 \times C \\
& + 0.267603681660816 \times B \times C^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E = & -1.3033911325751 + 9.74232503307444E && \text{Eq.(2.44)} \\
& - 06 \times L\%^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F = & 0 + 0.99590304675235 \times D && \text{Eq.(2.45)} \\
& + 0.0852214730608352 \times E + 0 * D^2 \\
& + 0 \times E^2 + 0 \times D * E + 0 \times D^3 \\
& + -0.0297749925104875 \times E^3 \\
& + 0 \times D^2 \times E + 0 \times D \times E^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
CI_{333} = & 0.34296644295302 && \text{Eq.(2.46)} \\
& + 0.0984845588190126 \times F \text{ (MAX} \\
& = 0.671, \text{MIN} = 0.064)
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.9 Map of soil water content at field capacity.

2.8 Water content at wilting point

The water content at wilting point $CCCC_{15000}$ is the water content of a soil when most plants growing in that soil wilt and fail to recover even if an additional amount of water is added afterwards. This is due to the fact that the plant is no more able to extract the water from the soil. The water content wilting point is also defined as the water content at $-1,500$ kPa (-15 bar) and calculated using the following formulas.

$$A = 3.77140361228726 \quad \text{Eq.(2.47)}$$

$$+ 0.819740344988767 \times \ln(Dg) C$$

$$B = -0.49157638336218 + 0.367695186350225 \times Corg\% \quad \text{Eq.(2.48)}$$

$$C = -2.905574766004 + 0.947767333204745 \times BD^3 \quad \text{Eq.(2.49)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D = & 0 + -0.763103574848119 \times A && \text{Eq.(2.50)} \\
 & + 0.236868672084561 \times B \\
 & + 0. -0.0731674247644929 * C \\
 & + 0 \times A^2 \\
 & + - 0.434887427284714 \times B^2 \\
 & + -0.105886229669014 \times C^2 \\
 & + 0.302936372100644 \times A \times B \\
 & + 0 \times A \times C \\
 & + - 0.483229853413334 \times B \times C \\
 & + 0.0494789265032567 \times A * B * C \\
 & + 0 \times A^3 \\
 & + -0.164404279418551 \times B^3 \\
 & + 0.0589897728741078 \times C^3 \\
 & + -0.221540878505337 * A^2 \times B \\
 & + 0.241483606228241 \times A \times B^2 \\
 & + 0 \times A \times C^2 + 0 \times A^2 \times C \\
 & + -0.334515879151902 \times B^2 \times C \\
 & + 0.150148733944991 \times B \times C^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 CI_{15000} = & 0.236463087248322 && \text{Eq.(2.51)} \\
 & + 0.104480408320589 \\
 & \times D (\text{MAX}.0.546; \text{MIN}.0.012)
 \end{aligned}$$

If

$$\theta_s + 0.01 > \text{poro2} \text{ Then } \theta_s = \text{poro2} \quad \text{Eq.(2.52)}$$

Else

$$\theta_s = \theta_s \quad \text{Eq.(2.53)}$$

If

$$\theta_r < \theta_s \text{ Then } \theta_r = \theta_r \quad \text{Eq.(2.54)}$$

Else

$$\theta_r = 0 \quad \text{Eq(2.55)}$$

Figure 2.10 Map of soil water content at wilting point.

CHAPTER 3

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW FEST MODULES

This chapter delves into the modeling framework employed for understanding stream-groundwater interactions and simulating hydrological processes within the Po River Basin. It introduces the integration of the MACCA-GW model into the FEST hydrological model and outlines the simulation scheme of the FEST model. The discussion encompasses the treatment of groundwater flow, percolation, and recharge mechanisms, along with the simulation of river-aquifer interaction dynamics. Additionally, it elaborates on the modular structure of the FEST model, emphasizing its adaptability to diverse hydrological contexts and the incorporation of meteorological input data for accurate simulations. The chapter elucidates key equations, boundary conditions, and computational procedures fundamental for hydrological analysis within the study area.

3.1 Stream-Groundwater interaction

In order to simulate groundwater flow, the MACCA-GW model by (Ravazzani, et al., 2011) was integrated into the FEST hydrological model. The MACCA-GW model is based on macroscopic cellular automata paradigm and was specifically developed for long time simulations.

In Neumann type boundary cells, the subsurface flow coming from hydrological simulation is transformed into a flux entering unconfined aquifer along the border. Dirichlet type boundary condition cells are set along the eastern border of the aquifer that continues downward into the Po valley. Piezometric head assigned to Dirichlet type cells is considered constant in time.

Figure 3.1 Map of the aquifer simulation domain (grey), Dirichlet type boundary condition cells (red) and Neumann type boundary condition cells (yellow)

In groundwater domain, percolation depurated from capillary rise computed by hydrological model is transformed into net recharge to groundwater storage.

In all cells adjacent to river network, river interconnection is simulated, which allows stream to gain or lose water. The stream stage is used to calculate the flux between the stream and the aquifer system, proportional to the head gradient between the river and the aquifer and a streambed conductance parameter. When the aquifer head is above the bottom of the streambed, model assumes that the discharge through the streambed is proportional to the difference in hydraulic head between the stream and the aquifer:

$$Q = \frac{K_{sb}LW}{M}(h_w - h) \quad \text{Eq. (3.1)}$$

where Q is the discharge [L^3T^{-1}] with a downward flux assumed positive, K_{sb} is the streambed hydraulic conductivity [LT^{-1}], L is the stream length [L], W is the stream width [L], M is the streambed thickness [L], h_w is the hydraulic head in the stream [L], and h is the hydraulic head in the aquifer [L]. If the aquifer head drops below the bottom of the streambed, the model assumes that the seepage flow is no longer proportional to the aquifer head and becomes dependent on the water level in the stream and the streambed thickness:

$$Q = \frac{K_{sb}LW}{M}(H_w + M) \quad \text{Eq. (3.2)}$$

where H_w is the water level in the stream above the surface of the streambed [L]. At the beginning of each iteration, terms representing river seepage are added to the groundwater flow equation for each cell containing a river reach. Negative seepage occurs when river stage drops below aquifer head. Groundwater seepage is added to or subtracted from river flow accordingly.

3.2 FEST Model scheme

The FEST model is a spatially distributed model. The simulation domain is discretized into regular square cells (typical application range: 10-5000 m) within which equations that describe hydrological processes are solved with a time step according to the available meteorological input data, the simulated processes, and the characteristics of the simulation domain (area, slope, etc..) that is usually set in the range 1 hour - 1 day. The FEST model is written in Fortran 90 with a modular approach so that only the dominant processes can be simulated for any specific studies (Figure 3.2). As an example, the snow module that simulates snow melt and accumulation is not relevant for simulating hydrological balance of a tropical river basin but it is fundamental when the simulation of snow melt is required for managing hydropower production over the Alpine mountains. For running a simulation, the FEST model requires meteorological input data. These can be site measurements acquired by meteorological stations or multidimensional raster data coming from weather forecast or climatic mathematical models. Station site data are interpolated over the simulation domain using different algorithms such as, Thiessen (1911) polygons, inverse distance weighted, or kriging methods. Specific methods are implemented to account for topographic effect on air temperature, solar radiation, and wind speed. Gridded air temperature data that are usually at a coarser spatial resolution than spatial step of hydrological simulation, are downscaled to higher resolution considering actual elevation from the digital elevation model. The snow module gets precipitation data, both from rain gauges and gridded dataset, and simulate snow accumulation, as snow water equivalent, and melting. The glacier module simulates glacier melting and interacts with snow module for glacier accumulation. The soil balance module computed evapotranspiration, infiltration, runoff, percolation and updates soil moisture. Some state variables are shared with plants module such as soil moisture and leaf area index, so that there is a mutual interaction between soil balance and plants modules. Drainage from soil balance is used as groundwater recharge. Runoff is the source term of routing module that simulates flow discharge. The resulting discharge time series can be affected by natural or artificial regulated reservoirs or bypass channels.

For more detailed information, please refer to the original site of [FEST model](#).

Figure 3.2 Scheme of hydrological processes implemented within FeST model with main state variables and input data.

CHAPTER 4

IDENTIFICATION OF IRRIGATION DISTRICT

This chapter intricately explores the management framework orchestrating agricultural irrigation across the vast expanse of the Po River Basin. It meticulously details the role of the *ConSORZI per la Bonifica e l'Irrigazione* in optimizing water resources, ensuring equitable distribution for crop irrigation while mitigating flooding risks. Furthermore, the chapter delves into the identification of pivotal diversion points along the basin's primary rivers, shedding light on their historical importance and operational intricacies. Through comprehensive analysis, this chapter offers insights into the foundational infrastructure sustaining agricultural vitality within the region.

4.1 Management system: reclamation and irrigation consortia

In Italy, the irrigation system is managed through the *ConSORZI per la Bonifica e l'Irrigazione*, institutions formed by landowners and other stakeholders, united with the aim of administering and promoting agricultural reclamation and irrigation projects. The main purpose of a *ConSORZIO* lies in optimizing the use of available water resources for crop irrigation and the control of surface and groundwater.

Their main activities include:

- Land Reclamation: this work involves the management of surface and groundwater in order to prevent flooding, drain swampy areas and regulate groundwater levels. This makes agricultural land cultivable and prevents flood damage.
- Irrigation: the *ConSORZI* take responsibility for the fair and efficient distribution of water resources to arable land. This facilitates farmers to grow their crops optimally, especially in regions with low rainfall.
- Maintenance of Water Infrastructure: consortia are in charge of maintaining canals, ditches, dams and other water infrastructure. This ensures the proper distribution of water and the proper functioning and safety of water works.
- Land Use Planning: the *ConSORZI* often contribute to land use planning and natural resource management. This may include establishing regulations and plans for sustainable use of water and land resources.
- Coordination among Farmers: consortia promote collaboration among member farmers, enabling them to share information, experiences and best practices regarding irrigation and water management.
- Representation of Interests: consortia act as spokespersons for their members to local, regional and national authorities, helping to ensure efficient management of water resources and promote sustainable agricultural development.

The organizational structure and responsibilities of a *ConSORZIO* may vary depending on local legislation and the specific needs of the area in which they operate.

4.1.1 Consortia in the Po River Basin

In the Po River Basin, the region surveyed is home to twelve *ConSORZI* that work for the multiple and sustainable use of water resources. They collaborate with five Regulatory Consortia that manage the dams of the large pre-Alpine lakes for optimal control, conservation and distribution of water resources. Some private *ConSORZI* contribute to irrigation, although they usually adhere to the rules of the larger organizations, with some exclusive concessions that do not significantly affect large scale.

The following list shows the main Consortia operating in the region:

- The *ConSORZIO Ovest-Sesia*, which mainly draws water from the Dora Baltea, Po and Sesia rivers.
- The *ConSORZIO Est-Sesia*, which mainly draws water from the Sesia, Po and Ticino rivers.
- The *ConSORZIO Ticino-Villoresi*, which mainly draws water from the Ticino and Adda rivers through the Villoresi Canal, Naviglio Grande, and Naviglio Pavese.
- The *ConSORZIO Media Pianura Bergamasca*, which mainly draws water from the Adda and Oglio rivers.

- The *Consorzio Dugali Naviglio Adda Serio*, which mainly draws water from the Oglio and Adda rivers.
- The *Consorzio Oglio-Mella*, which draws water from the Oglio and Mella rivers.
- The *Consorzio Chiese*, which manages water extraction from the Chiese River.
- The *Consorzio Chiese-Garda*, which draws water from the Oglio and Mincio rivers.
- The *Consorzio Muzza-Bassa Lodigiana*, which mainly manages the Muzza Canal and some works on the Po River.
- The *Consorzio Navarolo*, which draws water from the Po and Oglio rivers.
- The *Consorzio Territori sul Mincio*, which draws water from the Po, Mincio and Oglio rivers.
- The *Consorzio Terre dei Gonzaga Destra Po*, which manages water extraction along a short stretch of the Po River.

Each *Consorzio* publishes a variety of information on its website, including daily bulletins on water levels in the main streams from which water resources are withdrawn, as well as flow rates extracted through diversion works. Maximum abstraction rates that each facility must meet are also reported, ensuring that water is available for all users of the water supply. These flow rates are commonly referred to as "concession flow rates" and, in some cases, have never changed. Typically, they vary between the irrigation months of April to September and the non-working months.

The network that supports the entire irrigation system in Lombardia has more than 40,000 km of canals and 130 large hydroelectric and irrigation plants, whose function is to safeguard and irrigate an area of nearly 1,300,000 hectares.

4.2 Identification of major derivations

For the implementation of the model on an extensive and complex network, we chose to simplify it by focusing on the main detour works, represented as points along the watercourses, capable of evenly distributing the concession flows corresponding to the different areas they cover. This approach makes it possible to analyze, river by river, the amount of water withdrawn and its distribution in relation to the hectares of land to be irrigated.

4.2.1 Po River

Canale Cavour

The canal, inaugurated in 1863 and named in honor of Count Camillo Benso di Cavour, represents a remarkable hydraulic engineering project that played a crucial role in the economic development of the surrounding area and the irrigation of agricultural lands. With a length of 85 kilometers, it originates in the town of Civasso, northeast of Turin and Vercelli. The canal features numerous hydraulic works, such as locks and drains, as well as bridges that facilitate the transit of its waters through the vast agricultural territory of Piedmont, eventually flowing into the Ticino River.

Numerous diversions from the canal, in synergy with the Sesia River and its branches, made possible rice cultivation and industrial development in a formerly rural and economically depressed area. Nowadays, in addition to its irrigation function, the canal is an important tourist attraction, offering dedicated fishing and boating areas as well as popular bicycle routes. The concession flow rate is 110 m³ per second and the area served covers about 300,000 hectares (Antonaci, 2016). The intake facility is strategically located just before the confluence of the Dora Baltea River in order to minimize the impact of the canal on the hydrological regime of the Po River

4.2.2 Sesia River

Roggia Mora

It is one of the oldest examples of interconnection between watercourses, fed by the Sesia with a concession flow rate of 12 m³/s but traveling a distance of 60 km, intercepting the waters of the Strona, Agogna and Terdoppio streams before flowing with the waters of the Ticino. (Franzoni, 2012)

Roggia Biraga

Like all canals in the Novara area, it is mainly used for irrigation. Only recently, three hydropower plants have been added that generate electricity from the canal's flow. The allowed flow rate is 27 m³/s. Along its course, it receives additional contribution from the Cavour Canal and Busca Canal, and ends its course in the Agogna Stream. In total, it extends for 51 km. (Franzoni, 2012)

Roggia Busca

It is one of the main canals in the area in terms of extracted flow, with a flow rate of 34 m³/s. Along its course, it meets the Cavour Canal, from which it can receive about 30 m³/s of flow in case of high irrigation needs. Subsequently, it joins and merges with the Roggia Biraga, then divides into two branches: the first re-enters the Sesia, while the second continues into the Lomellina. Altogether, the route extends for about 54 km, from its mouth in the Sesia River to its confluence with the Roggia Biraga. (Franzoni, 2012)

Roggione di Sartirana

This is the southernmost diversion of the Sesia River. It has a length of about 27 km, with an allowed flow rate of 27 m³/s. Along its course, it meets the Gamarra stream as a tributary, finally reaching the Lomellina. (Franzoni, 2012)

4.2.3 Ticino River

Canale Villoresi

It was designed in the 19th century mainly for irrigation and water use purposes but has taken on different functions over the years. It stretches for about 80 km, connecting the city of Milan to the Ticino River to the northwest. Its construction had a significant impact on agriculture and water supply in the surrounding area. It has been used to irrigate farmland, to provide drinking water to local communities, and to support industry. During irrigation months, it withdraws 64 m³/s of water from the Ticino River through the Panperduto Dam. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

Canale Regina Margherita

It is an irrigation canal that flows in the province of Novara. It came into operation in 1954 when the Porto della Torre dam was completed. It has a length of about 25 kilometers, with an inlet flow rate of 70 m³/s, which decreases to 45 m³/s after the Alto Novarese branch. Its waters eventually flow into the Cavour Canal. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

Naviglio Grande

It is one of the four main irrigation and transportation canals that make up the Milanese Navigli system, dating mainly from the medieval and Renaissance periods. Built in the 12th century, the Naviglio Grande stretches for about 50 kilometers, connecting the city of

Milan to the Ticino River. Originally conceived for agricultural and water purposes, the canal played a crucial role in the region's economic development, enabling the transportation of goods such as lumber, coal and building materials between Milan and the Ticino River. It has a permitted flow rate of 64 m³/s. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

Naviglio Sforzesco

It originates from the Ticino River in Galliate and flows south for a length of 27 km, crossing territories divided between Piedmont and Lombardy. After passing through the city of Vigevano, the canal divides into two branches, with one returning to the Ticino River, while the other distributes into irrigation canals in the Lomellina countryside. Its allowed flow rate is 9.42 m³/s. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

Naviglio Langosco

The canal begins its course in the town of Turbigo, irrigating the countryside of Novara and Lomellina. It then re-enters the territory of Lombardy, also passing through the city of Vigevano, and ends in the countryside of Tromello. It has a length of 23 km and an allowed flow rate of 22.7 m³/s. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

Roggia Magna

An ancient canal dating back to the 15th century, it has always been used to convey water from rivers to agricultural lands. It has a granted flow rate of 10.8 m³/s and is characterized by numerous branches that allow widespread distribution of water resources. (Consorzio del Ticino, 1999)

4.2.4 Adda River

Fosso Bergamasco

It is an artificial canal connecting the Adda River to the Serio River and later to the Oglio River. It was built in the 13th century and, for a long time, marked the border between the Duchy of Milan and the Republic of Venice. It has a length of 35 km and a permitted flow rate of 10 m³/s.

Naviglio Martesana

Also known as Naviglio Piccolo, it is part of the artificial canal system that connects Milan to the river system of the Lombardy region. It originates in the municipality of Trezzo sull'Adda and reaches Porta Nuova in Milan, covering a distance of 38 km with an allowed flow rate of 32 m³/s. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

Roggia Vailata

An ancient canal that has always been used to distribute water resources in the Bergamo countryside. It takes water at the confluence of the Brembo and the Adda, runs about 15 km, and has a granted flow rate of about 9.5 m³/s. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

Canale Retorto

It forms the western branch of the Roggia Comuna, drawing water in the municipality of Cassano d'Adda. It has a total length of 14 km and a permitted flow rate of 18 m³/s. A hydroelectric power plant is located along its course, followed immediately by the Pandina and Cremasca canals. The northeastern branch of the Roggia Comuna originates from springs known as Fontanili, typical of this region. Once joined, the canal crosses a number of fields to the "Three Mouths" location, so named because of the division of water into three canals that allow water to be distributed over an incredibly large area. The main branch has a length of about 22 km, an allowed flow rate of 11.6 m³/s, and covers an area of 3,700 hectares. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

Canale Muzza

It is the largest diversion from the Adda River. It takes water from the hamlet of Gropello d'Adda, near the town of Cassano d'Adda. It has a total length of 60 km and a permitted flow rate of 112 m³/s. It is one of the oldest canals ever built, with the earliest construction work dating back to Roman times. In fact, it is a natural branch that has been modified by mankind for better management of water resources. Along its course, it meets the Vacchelli Canal, to which it transfers part of its flow. Its natural course ends in the municipality of Melegnano, where it flows into the Lambro River. Hydraulic engineering works now allow a second branch, which, thanks to the Paullo lock, turns 90° southeast and continues into the province of Lodi before returning to the Adda. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

Roggia Rivoltana

A canal dating back to the 15th century that stretches for about 28 km. It takes water from the municipality of Rivolta d'Adda and has a permitted flow rate of 7 m³/s. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

Canale Vacchelli

This is a relatively modern canal, built between 1887 and 1892. It has a length of about 34 km, diverts water near the town of Merlino, and has a granted flow rate of 38.5 m³/s, allowing the irrigation of 80,000 hectares. Along its course, it is partly fed by the Muzza Canal, crosses the Serio River, and ends in the province of Cremona, flowing into the province's navigable system. Thanks to prudent management of the canal, its waters now exhibit good quality and are rich in valuable fish species. The waterway is, in fact, the focus of various conservation efforts aimed at preserving native fish species such as carp and Italian pike. (Consorzio dell'Adda, 1990)

4.2.5 Oglio River

Along the first part of its course, the river feeds a system of canals called the "Serieole of the upper Brescian plain."

Roggia Fusia

It is the only canal that comes directly out of Lake Iseo. It has a length of about 10 km and irrigates an area of about 4,237 hectares with a granted flow of 8.02 m³/s. (Ravelli, 2020)

Roggia Vetra

The oldest and largest in terms of flow rate among the main canals branching off from the Oglio River. The flow rate granted is 10.84 m³/s, covering an irrigated area of 2,900 hectares. (Ravelli, 2020)

Roggia Castrina

Beginning in the municipality of Palazzolo sull'Oglio, just like the Roggia Vetra, it has a length of 25 km and serves 2,300 hectares of countryside with a granted flow rate of 4.22 m³/s. (Ravelli, 2020)

Roggia Travagliana

Also originating in the municipality of Palazzolo sull'Oglio, it is an extension of the former Seriola Galbena. It has a length of 25 km and covers 1,900 hectares of land with a granted flow rate of 6.20 m³/s. To easily identify the areas covered by each diversion, these last three canals are considered as one. (Ravelli, 2020)

Rogge Castellana e Vescovada

These are the last canals in the Chiari area. They originate in the municipality of Pontoglio and provide numerous basins, ditches, and "dugali". The total flow rate granted is 9.43 m³/s. (Ravelli, 2020)

Minor derivations

The discharge capacity of the Oglio River is 86 m³/s, at least half of which is diverted into numerous secondary channels whose served territory is difficult to identify. These include the "Naviglio Cremona," the "Naviglio di Calcio," and the "Cavo Molinara," which have intake structures located fairly close to each other and a combined flow rate of 15.56 m³/s. For these reasons, they are considered as a single branch. These are the latest channels in the Chiari area. They originate in the municipality of Pontoglio and supply numerous basins, ditches, and 'dugali.' The total permitted flow rate is 9.43 m³/s. (Ravelli, 2020)

4.2.6 Serio River

The Serio canal system and its branches serve primarily for irrigation purposes during the summer season (about 3 months per year) for a significant portion of the agricultural land south of Bergamo. During the remaining periods (about 9 months per year), the continuous presence of water in the dense network of canals maintains the canal ecosystem, serves sanitation purposes, and, most importantly, during intense atmospheric precipitation events, diverts excessive runoff from the designated catchment area (which includes roads, sewer overlays, land, urban surfaces, etc.). (Consorzio di Bonifica della Media Pianura Bergamasca)

Roggia Serio Grande

The "Roggia Serio Grande" originates at the Albino intake structure. On the right bank (orographic side) of the Serio River, it flows through the municipalities of Albino, Nembro, Alzano Lombardo, Ranica, Torre Boldone and Bergamo. Treviolo is home to the last irrigation diversions and the discharge point of the Serio Canal, which collects rainwater, excessive sewage runoff and excess flows conveyed by the canal before discharging them into the Brembo

River. It covers an area of about 6,000 hectares. (Consorzio di Bonifica della Media Pianura Bergamasca)

Roggia Morlana

The Roggia Morlana originates at the Albino intake structure. On the right bank (orographic side) of the Serio River, it flows through the municipalities of Albino, Nembro, Alzano Lombardo, Ranica, Bergamo, Gorle, Seriate, Orio al Serio, Grassobbio, Stezzano, Zanica, Levate and Ugnano. It covers an area of about 4,000 hectares. (Consorzio di Bonifica della Media Pianura Bergamasca)

Roggia Borgogna

The Borgogna Canal originates at the Albino intake structure on the right bank (orographic side) of the Serio River. After supplying water to some hydroelectric power plants on the left bank, it returns water flow to the Serio River. At Villa di Serio, it is again and permanently diverted from the river through a specific intake structure. In the territory of Pedrengo, there is another intake structure on the river to supplement the flow during the irrigation period (Patera Canal of Brusaporto). It flows through the municipalities of Albino, Pradalunga, Villa di Serio, Scanzorosciate, Pedrengo, Seriate, Albano Sant'Alessandro, Brusaporto, Montello, Costa di Mezzate, Bagnatica, Cavernago, Calcinate, Bolgare, Ghisalba, and Mornico al Serio, finally discharging its flow into the Zerra outlet canal, the Serio River, the Mornichello ditch, and the Zerra stream. It covers an area of about 8,000 hectares. (Consorzio di Bonifica della Media Pianura Bergamasca)

For simplicity of implementation in the model, the three canals are considered as a single entity to more easily identify the area covered, with a total flow rate of 20 m³/s.

4.2.7 Chiese River

Roggia Borgogna

The first is a system of man-made canals that connect the Chiese River to the Oglio River, allowing irrigation of a large agricultural area in the Brescia region. The second is a diversion that flows between the provinces of Mantua and Brescia. The managing consortium has agreed on a total granted flow rate of 28.7 m³/s, leaving it up to local authorities to agree on the distribution of water resources. (Consorzio di bonifica Chiese, 2018)

4.2.8 Mincio River

Canale Virgilio

Originating in the municipality of Monzambano, at the Salionze dam, this watercourse was initially designed to connect the Mincio to the Po River in the territory of Mantua. The watercourse has a length of 18 km, a permitted flow rate of 24 m³/s and serves an area of 44,000 hectares. (Consorzio di bonifica Territori sul Mincio, 2018)

Fossa di Pozzolo

Built in the 15th century, it is still a powerful system of dams and structures that distribute the waters of the Mincio River throughout the Alto Mantovano, with a granted flow rate of 20 m³/s. (Consorzio di bonifica Territori sul Mincio, 2018)

Naviglio di Isola di Goito

This is an artificial canal that allows the connection and management of water flow from the Mincio River to Lake Superior in Mantua. It has a concession flow rate of 8.7 m³/s. (Consorzio di bonifica Territori sul Mincio, 2018)

Minor derivations

Like the Chiese River, there are also numerous small diversions on the Mincio River, which individually may have a minor impact on the river's hydrological regime, but when combined, significantly affect it. To provide a more complete representation of the channel system, the Cantagallo and Curtagone diversions, with respective discharge capacities of 8.3 and 3.5 m³/s, were also included. (Consorzio di bonifica Territori sul Mincio, 2018)

4.3 Identification of areas irrigated by each derivation

The next phase of research aims to delineate the spatial extents irrigated by the main branches of the major tributaries of the Po River, with particular emphasis on their interaction with agricultural areas. To conduct this investigation, a diverse range of data sources was exploited, including land cover information provided by the Dusaf Project, specifically for the

Lombardy region, and the Corine Landcover Project for regions outside the Lombardy area, such as the Novarese area, known for its significant rice production.

Initially, the data collection phase was of primary importance, involving the acquisition of shapefiles through the geoportals of the Lombardy and Piedmont regions. Next, the filtering phase of agricultural areas was carried out, based on the categorization used in the projects.

Next, the focus was on identifying the agricultural areas irrigated by each of the main derivations. For each work, all agricultural areas adjacent to the course of the main canal and its branches were considered irrigated.

Finally, a validation process of the results was conducted, making use of the data available on the portals of the Reclamation Consortia. This phase proved essential to verify the accuracy of the identified areas and make any improvements or refinements to the spatial analysis method used.

The derivations used to validate the results obtained from this analysis are shown below in the table.

Table 4.1 Results of the calculation method for the irrigated areas by each diversion in comparison with literature data.

RIVER	DERIVATION NAME	WATERFLOW CONCESSION [M3/S]	CALCULATED IRRIGATED AREA [HE]	IRRIGATED AREA BY BIBLIOGRAPHY [HE]
Po	Canale Cavour	110	222077	300000
Sesia	Roggia Mora	12	27995	
Sesia	Roggia Biraga	27	25803	
Sesia	Roggia Busca	34	126298	
Sesia	Roggione di Sartirana	27	135274	
Ticino	Villoresi	64	24500	
Ticino	Regina Elena	70	136782	
Ticino	Naviglio Grande	64	61205	
Ticino	Naviglio Sforzesco	9.42	124280	
Ticino	Naviglio Langosco	22.7	123508	
Ticino	Roggia Magna	10.8	125869	
Adda	Fosso Bergamasco	10	13182.4	
Adda	Naviglio Martesana	32	86157	
Adda	Roggia Vailata	9.5	9489.8	
Adda	Canale Retorto	18	26589.7	16500
Adda	Canale Muzza	112	42444	
Adda	Roggia Rivoltana	7	1694.5	
Adda	Canale Vacchelli	38.5	105340.6	80000
Oglio	Roggia Fusia	8.02	8454	4237
Oglio	Roggia Vetra, Castrina e Travagliana	21.26	41367	18300
Oglio	Roggia Castellana e Vescovada	9.43	10803	
Oglio	Minor derivations	17.56	17357	

Chiese	Naviglio Bresciano e Roggia Lonata	28.7	62822	
Mincio	Canale Virgilio	24	74676	44000
Mincio	Fossa di Pozzolo	20	30684	20000
Mincio	Naviglio di Goito	8.7	9166	
Mincio	Cantagallo	8.3	6301	
Mincio	Curtagone	3.5	2984	
Serio	Minor derivations	20	31493	18000

The results obtained are, where comparison is possible, of the same order of magnitude with respect to the bibliographic data despite numerous uncertainty factors such as the presence of fountains, the presence of minor consortia that irrigate land autonomously, and the use in small part of irrigation techniques other than gravity irrigation considered here. (Gandolfi, 2017)

Given the vast complexity of the canal network present in the study area, this methodology offers significant simplification while maintaining replicability of results. Further refinement, especially in areas such as Novarese, could represent a possible future improvement of the model. However, it should be noted that the current level of detail is beyond the objectives of this project.

Figure 4.1 Map representing the 21 more extended irrigated areas

CHAPTER 5

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The implementation of the new irrigation section in the model necessitates the calibration of parameters governing the interaction of water flow with the underlying aquifer. This segment extensively delves into these parameters, elucidating their physical significance and how they influence river flows.

The resulting data is scrutinized by comparing it with a reference simulation termed 'standard.' This simulation represents the outcomes derived from maintaining the parameters at their initial values. The comparison involves evaluating variations in annual peak flows for each section and discrepancies in cumulative volumes passing through each section during the 2011-2015 temporal horizon.

Assessing the results against the standard simulation enables a critical evaluation of parameter modifications. By analyzing variations in annual peak flows, the impact of alterations on water resource management during peak conditions is gauged. Meanwhile, disparities in cumulative volumes provide insights into overall water resource management over the specified temporal horizon, shedding light on the efficacy of the new parameter settings.

This analytical approach establishes a robust framework for comprehending the specific contributions of parameter changes to hydrological dynamics and the efficiency of the irrigation system.

To ensure immediate, easily interpretable statistics facilitating comparisons among simulations, the following aggregation processes have been implemented:

- Annual peak flows, to gauge how well the model replicates flood phenomena, the percentage difference ($\Delta\%$) between the standard simulation and each other simulated peak flood is calculated for each year and measurement station. The mean and variance of all $\Delta\%$ values are then computed, providing two straightforward indicators of the simulation's behavior concerning this phenomenon.

- Cumulative volumes, to assess how well the model replicates the cumulative volumes measured by the measurement stations, the $\Delta\%$ on the last day of simulation for all measurement stations is calculated. The arithmetic sum of these $\Delta\%$ values is then computed, providing a term that explains the general behavior and indicate whether the measurement stations exhibit consistent values among themselves or not.

These statistics, specifically the $\Delta\%$ values, are referenced to the standard simulation, as the sensitivity analysis aims to understand how parameter variations reflect in the results. Comparing these findings with observed values will be crucial for calibration, ultimately ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the model.

5.1 Deep percolation factor

In the FEST model, soil water balance is managed by dividing the soil into two basic parts. The first, surface, is the root zone depth, where water is available to surface vegetation and is subject to processes such as percolation, infiltration and evapotranspiration. The second, deeper, is known as transmission zone depth and represents the portion of the ground involved in groundwater flows, acting as a link between the various cells in the presence of slopes and connecting the root zone with the underground aquifer. Recharge of the latter occurs mainly through the process of deep percolation, which is computationally represented in the FEST model by the deep percolation factor.

The balance of water content within the root zone and transmission zone, per unit area, is calculated according to the following equations:

$$\theta_{t+1}^{rz} = \theta_t^{rz} + \frac{I - ET - P + CR + TSE - RSE}{RZD} * \Delta t \quad \text{Eq.(5.1)}$$

$$\theta_{t+1}^{tz} = \theta_t^{tz} + \frac{P - TSE - DP}{RZD} * \Delta t \quad \text{Eq.(5.2)}$$

where θ_{t+1}^{rz} , θ_t^{rz} , θ_t^{tz} e θ_{t+1}^{tz} are the soil moisture of the root and transmission zone at time $t + 1$ and t , respectively; I infiltration (m/s); ET effective evapotranspiration (m/s); P is the percolation from the root zone calculated as effective hydraulic conductivity according to the Brooks and Corey water retention curve; DP is percolation out of the transmission zone, calculated as hydraulic conductivity at saturation, multiplied by a coefficient that takes into account the degree of fracturing of the rock substrate (0 for impermeable rock substrate, 1 for fully permeable rock substrate); CR is the capillary upflow; TSE and RSE are the transmission and root zone excess saturation, respectively; RZD and TZD are the root and transmission zone depth (m), respectively; Δt is the time step duration from t to $t + 1$. RSE is added to the runoff

to account for the mechanism of runoff formation more than saturation. The Figure 18 represent the conceptual scheme of this phenomenon.

This factor is described within a mask. By default, it is set equal to 0 along the slopes, in when a nearly impermeable rocky substrate is present, and equal to 1 in the lowland cells, where a sandy substrate is present. However, while for lowland cells the value makes sense, along the slope the value can be changed since aquifer recharge also occurs in those areas. (Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering)

Figure 5.1 Soil balance scheme of cell on hillslope(up) and of a cell on land plain (down) RZD = root zone depth, TZD = transmission zone depth, I = infiltration, ET = evapotranspiration, RSE = saturation excess from root zone, P = percolation, TSE = saturation excess from transmission zone, LF_{IN} =input lateral flux, LF_{OUT} = output lateral flux, DP = deep percolation.

5.1.1 Results and comments

To analyze the impact of the deep percolation factor, it was varied across different values (1, 0.5, 0.125, 0.075). The modifications aimed to evaluate the changes at various measurement stations compared to the initial simulation with no deep percolation along the hillslope. It is expected that changes in the deep percolation factor will affect the annual peak flows and cumulative volumes due to variations in water infiltration and groundwater recharge.

Table 5.1 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	-38%	-62%	-14%	-58%	-24%
PIACENZA	-32%	-65%	-21%	-56%	-12%
CREMONA	-28%	-70%	-30%	-58%	-64%
BORETTO	-25%	-70%	-41%	-60%	-50%
BORGOFORTE	-26%	-74%	-47%	-63%	-57%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-30%	-67%	-54%	-59%	-64%

Table 5.2 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	-45%
PIACENZA	-46%
CREMONA	-49%
BORETTO	-49%
BORGOFORTE	-49%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-48%

As stated at the beginning of the chapter, this data has been aggregated to facilitate quick comparisons among the simulations and intuitively understand the effect of changing the deep percolation factor on the model outputs. This process yields the following values for the example provided in the tables above.

Table 5.3 Aggregated value for the evaluation of deep percolation factor effect on the waterflow

AGGREGATED VALUE	
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	-47%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	3% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	-284%

Regarding cumulative volumes, the effect is consistent, with a $\Delta\%$ ranging from -45% to -49%.

Concerning peak flows, the effect is also relatively consistent, with a general decrease varying from -12% in Piacenza in 2015 to -74% in Borgoforte in 2012.

The analysis revealed that the average of peak flow $\Delta\%$ and the sum of $\Delta\%$ on cumulative volumes showed a flat trend, indicating very low sensitivity to the specific value assigned.

Figure 5.2 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of deep percolation factor.

The significant impact on the results was observed when applying a deep percolation factor along the slopes, rather than the actual value of the factor itself. This suggests that the presence of the deep percolation factor is what influences the outcomes, while variations in its specific value do not significantly alter the results.

For the continuation of the procedure, the deep percolation factor is set at 0.075. This simulation will be considered the new standard simulation for subsequent analyses. This decision is made because without activating deep percolation, the soil would almost always reach saturation, reducing the effect of varying other parameters on the model output.

5.2 SCS Curve Number

The SCS Curve Number (SCS-CN) is one of the widely used models for calculating surface runoff. According to this method, infiltration is calculated as the difference between precipitation and runoff. The SCS-CN method does not take into account the intensity or duration of precipitation; it only considers total precipitation.

$$I = P_{TOT} - R \quad \text{Eq.(5.3)}$$

$$R = \frac{(P - I_a)^2}{P - I_a + S} \quad \text{Eq.(5.4)}$$

With

$$I_a = 0.2 * S \quad \text{Eq.(5.5)}$$

where I is the total infiltration [L], P is the total precipitation [L], R is the runoff [L], S is the maximum water retention capacity of the soil [L] and IA is the water initially contained in the soil.

S is a function of CN according to the following formula:

$$S = S_0 * \left(\frac{100}{CN} - 1 \right) \quad \text{Eq.(5.6)}$$

with $S_0=254$ mm.

The portion of rainfall not transformed into runoff is considered as infiltration into the soil. The values of the CN parameter are derived from graphical representations of the correlation between rainfall amount and surface flow. The CN parameter is closely related to land use. Its value changes according to pre-existing moisture conditions. CNII represents average soil moisture conditions (AMC II) for the previous five days, while CNI refers to dry soil conditions (AMC I) and CNIII describes high moisture conditions (AMC III). To accommodate different land uses and climatic variations, the SCS-CN method has undergone several modifications (Soulis, 2012). Several scholars have developed a modified version of the SCS-CN for continuous simulations (Adornado, 2010). The model proposed by Ravazzani et al. (Ravazzani, 2007) has been implemented within the FeST model. According to this approach, at each time step, it is calculated based on the degree of soil saturation, represented by ε_t .

$$S = S_1 - \varepsilon_t * (S_1 - S_2) \quad \text{Eq.(5.7)}$$

With

$$S_1 = S(CN_I) \quad \text{Eq.(5.8)}$$

$$S_2 = S(CN_{II}) \quad \text{Eq.(5.9)}$$

$$CN_I = CN_{II} - \left(20 * \frac{100 - CN_{II}}{100 - CN_{II} + e^{2.533 - 0.0626 * (100 - CN_{II})}}\right) \quad \text{Eq.(5.10)}$$

$$CN_{III} = CN_{II} * e^{0.00673 * (100 - CN_{II})} \quad \text{Eq.(5.11)}$$

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{\theta_t - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} \quad \text{Eq.(5.12)}$$

where θ_t is the actual water content at time t , θ_s is the maximum saturated water content and θ_r is the residual water content. At the same time, CNII values are defined according to the land cover classes identified in the CORINE project.

5.2.1 Results and comments

To analyze the impact of varying the CN parameter, an offset was applied to the parameter mask, with extreme values of +10 and -10. This means an increase or decrease of 10 in the CN value for each cell of the mask representing the Po River basin, up to the closure section of Pontelagoscuro. The expected impact includes significant changes in annual peak flows and cumulative volumes, as the CN parameter greatly influences the model's ability to simulate runoff and infiltration.

Table 5.4 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with offset = -10

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	-13%	-11%	-10%	-1%	-14%
PIACENZA	-14%	-38%	-8%	-21%	-1%
CREMONA	-14%	-24%	-20%	-20%	-13%
BORETTO	-14%	-1%	-23%	-23%	-2%
BORGOFORTE	-15%	-8%	-24%	-24%	-3%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-18%	-25%	-32%	-32%	-5%

Table 5.5 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with offset = -10

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	-1%
PIACENZA	-2%
CREMONA	-3%
BORETTO	-3%
BORGOFORTE	-3%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-3%

Table 5.6 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with offset = +10

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	24%	50%	24%	18%	2%
PIACENZA	13%	57%	23%	23%	1%
CREMONA	13%	70%	23%	23%	24%
BORETTO	13%	33%	26%	30%	21%
BORGOFORTE	14%	39%	27%	35%	36%
PONTELAGOSCURO	16%	38%	31%	40%	34%

Table 5.7 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with offset = +10

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	12%
PIACENZA	12%
CREMONA	14%
BORETTO	15%
BORGOFORTE	13%
PONTELAGOSCURO	12%

To better understand the behavior of this parameter, simulations with offset values of +5 and -5 were also conducted, with only the aggregated values reported to streamline the explanation. The graph representing the values from the table is also included, making it easier to visualize the effect of the parameter on flow values.

Table 5.8 Aggregated value for the evaluation of CN variations effect on the waterflow in comparison between the four simulations.

AGGREGATED VALUE	-10	-5	+5	+10
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	-13%	-8%	11%	27%

ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	2% ²	1% ²	1% ²	2% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	-15%	-9%	26%	79%

Figure 5.3 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of CN offset.

The data indicates that applying an offset to the CN parameter significantly impacts both annual peak flows and cumulative volumes. Specifically, increasing the CN value by 10 results in substantial increases in annual peak flows, with a maximum increase of 70% at Cremona in 2012, while decreasing the CN value by 10 leads to significant reductions in peak flows, with a maximum decrease of -38% at Piacenza in 2011. This suggests that the CN parameter has a considerable influence on the model's ability to simulate flood peaks.

Regarding cumulative volumes, the effect is more consistent and pronounced with the positive offset, where an increase of 12-15% is observed across all stations. The negative offset results in a minor decrease in cumulative volumes, ranging from -1% to -3%.

In summary, the sensitivity analysis reveals that the CN parameter significantly affects annual peak flows more than cumulative volumes. The results underscore the importance of accurately calibrating this parameter to ensure reliable model outputs, particularly for predicting flood peaks and managing water resources effectively.

Figure 5.4 Simulated discharge with different offset values in 2014.

Figure 5.5 Cumulated volumes with different offset values in the calibration period 2011-2015.

5.3 Hydraulic conductivity

The water retention curve, also known as soil moisture characteristic, establishes the relationship between soil water content (θ) and soil water potential (suction) ψ . This curve illustrates the behavior of different soil types in relation to their moisture content. When the potential is close to zero, the soil tends toward saturation and water is retained mainly by capillary forces. As θ decreases, water binding becomes stronger. At lower potentials, closer to the withering point, water is retained strongly in smaller pores, at grain contact points, and in the form of films bound by adsorptive forces around the particles. Several models characterize the shape of water retention curves, and one such model, the Brooks and Corey (1964) model, is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = \left(\frac{\psi}{\psi_a}\right)^B \quad \text{Eq.(5.13)}$$

Where θ_r and θ_s represent residual moisture and saturated soil moisture, respectively, measured in (m³/m³). ψ indicates the soil suction (m), ψ_a is the air inlet pressure (m), and B represents the pore size distribution index (-).

The equation governing the hydraulic conductivity of partially saturated soil, $K(\psi)$ (m/s), is expressed as:

$$K(\psi) = \begin{cases} K_s * \left(\frac{\psi_a}{\psi}\right)^{2+3*B} & \psi \leq \psi_a \\ K_s & \psi > \psi_a \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq.(5.14)}$$

Where K_s (m/s) represents the hydraulic conductivity of saturated soil.

5.3.1 Results and comments

Introduction

To analyze the impact of hydraulic conductivity, a scale factor was applied to the soil permeability mask $K(\psi)$ (m/s). Considering an acceptable uncertainty of two orders of magnitude, the maximum variation range for the scale factor was defined as 0.01-10. The expected impact includes notable changes in both annual peak flows and cumulative volumes due to variations in infiltration and percolation processes.

Table 5.9 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 0.01

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	73%	174%	74%	144%	33%
PIACENZA	59%	199%	76%	132%	21%
CREMONA	49%	242%	78%	139%	215%
BORETTO	37%	245%	90%	149%	149%
BORGOFORTE	40%	290%	101%	171%	160%
PONTELAGOSCURO	46%	196%	139%	139%	181%

Table 5.10 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 0.01

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	71%
PIACENZA	74%
CREMONA	85%
BORETTO	85%
BORGOFORTE	82%
PONTELAGOSCURO	79%

Table 5.11 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 10

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	-24%	-17%	-11%	-1%	-3%
PIACENZA	-24%	-27%	-16%	-34%	-1%
CREMONA	-24%	-25%	-50%	-37%	-1%
BORETTO	-25%	-2%	-60%	-59%	-25%
BORGOFORTE	-27%	-11%	-57%	-57%	-19%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-31%	-30%	-58%	-41%	-1%

Table 5.12 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with scale factor = 10

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	-28%
PIACENZA	-31%
CREMONA	-35%
BORETTO	-34%
BORGOFORTE	-33%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-33%

To better understand the behavior of this parameter, simulation with scale factor of 0.1 was also conducted, with only the aggregated values reported to streamline the explanation. The

graph representing the values from the table is also included, making it easier to visualize the effect of the parameter on flow values.

Table 5.13 Aggregated value for the evaluation of conductivity variations effect on the waterflow in comparison between the three simulations

AGGREGATED VALUE	0.01	0.1	10
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	128%	35%	-27%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	51% ²	5% ²	4% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	476%	44%	-193%

Figure 5.6 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of Permeability scale factor.

These results indicate that hydraulic conductivity significantly influences the hydrological behavior of the model, particularly in terms of infiltration and percolation processes, results in notable changes in both annual peak flows and cumulative volumes. Specifically, the annual peak flows showed a consistent variation across all measurement stations, with the highest reduction observed at Pontelagoscuro in 2012 (-55%) and the highest increasing at Borgoforte in 2012(+290%). Cumulative volumes also varied a lot, with Δ% values ranging from -20% at Pontelagoscuro for the 10-scale factor simulation to the +85% at Boretto and Piacenza for the 0.01-scale factor simulation.

Figure 5.7 Simulated discharge with different scale factor values in 2014.

Figure 5.8 Cumulative volumes with different scale factor values in the calibration period 2011-2015.

5.4 Interaction river-aquifer

Rivers contribute or drain water from the groundwater system, depending on the hydraulic gradient between the river and the groundwater regime. The quantification of river/aquifer current hydraulics is an important problem in the study of alluvial aquifers and the assessment of river baseflow.

In all cells adjacent to the river network, river interconnection is simulated, which allows the stream to gain or lose water. River height is used for direction and modulus of interaction flow, which is proportional to the hydraulic gradient between the river and the aquifer and to a riverbed conductivity parameter. When the pressure of the aquifer is greater than the height of the water from the riverbed, the model assumes that the discharge through the riverbed is proportional to the hydraulic pressure difference between the stream and the aquifer:

$$Q = \frac{k_s * L * W}{M} * (h_w + h) \quad \text{Eq.(5.15)}$$

where Q represents the discharge [L³T⁻¹] with downward flow assumed to be positive, k_s is the hydraulic conductivity of the riverbed [LT⁻¹], L is the river length [L], W is the river width [L], M is the riverbed thickness [L], h_w is the hydraulic head in the stream [L], and h is the hydraulic head in the aquifer [L]. If the head of the aquifer falls below the bottom of the riverbed, the model assumes that the percolative flow is no longer proportional to the head of the aquifer, but depends on the water level in the watercourse and the thickness of the riverbed:

$$Q = \frac{k_s * L * W}{M} * (h_w + M) \quad \text{Eq.(5.16)}$$

where H_w represents the water level in the stream above the surface of the riverbed [L]. At the beginning of each iteration, terms representing fluvial percolation are added to the groundwater flow equation for each cell that contains a river section. Negative percolation occurs when the river level falls below the head of the aquifer. Groundwater percolation is added or subtracted accordingly to the river flow.

Figure 5.9 Conceptual representation of river-aquifer interconnection: Q is the discharge, L is the stream length, W is the stream width, M is the streambed thickness, h_w is the hydraulic head in the stream, and h is the hydraulic head in the aquifer.

5.4.1 Results and comments

The effect of activating this process has, theoretically, a dual impact:

- during floods, when the water pressure in the river is greater than that of the aquifer, part of the flood is discharged from the river to the aquifer, at least partially reducing the river flow;
- at the same time, during normal and drought periods, the aquifer has higher pressure and recharges the river.

The rate at which water volume shifts occur is also referred to as “conductivity,” and modifying its value is the subject of this paragraph. However, just like with the deep percolation factor, it is necessary to study a double sensitivity. The first step involves the activation of the process compared to the standard simulation and, only subsequently, evaluating a variation of one order of magnitude compared to the initial conductivity value, initially set at 10^{-6} , to understand what effect its modification might have.

Table 5.14 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with a river-aquifer conductivity of 10^{-6}

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	-12%	-15%	-11%	-11%	-17%
PIACENZA	-14%	-17%	-13%	-12%	-20%
CREMONA	-15%	-20%	-16%	-13%	-21%
BORETTO	-13%	-26%	-20%	-16%	-15%
BORGOFORTE	-15%	-29%	-23%	-17%	-16%
PONTELAGOSCURO	-20%	-35%	-33%	-21%	-24%

Table 5.15 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume for each measure station for the simulation with a river-aquifer conductivity of 10^{-6}

MEASURE STATION	
SPESSA PO	2%
PIACENZA	3%
CREMONA	4%
BORETTO	3%
BORGOFORTE	3%
PONTELAGOSCURO	1%

The conductivity value was modified, varying it from 10^{-7} to 10^{-5} to understand the sensitivity of the results to this parameter, as shown in the following figure.

Table 5.16 Aggregated value for the evaluation of river-aquifer conductivity effect on the waterflow in comparison between the three simulations.

AGGREGATED VALUE	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-7}
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	-20%	-18%	-1%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	2% ²	0% ²	0% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	125%	16%	6%

Figure 5.10 Graphic visualization of aggregated value regarding variation of river-aquifer conductivity.

For both $\Delta\%$ tables, the result is exactly as theorized earlier, with flood peaks being mitigated by the aquifer and cumulative volumes slightly increasing due to the normal flow from the aquifer to the river.

For this section, the graph of the aquifer height for each simulation is also provided. By activating the interaction process, the height decreases significantly, which is logical since the increase in cumulative volumes is due to the aquifer recharging the river, and therefore its height decreases accordingly.

Figure 5.11 Simulated discharge with different conductivity values in 2014.

Figure 5.12 Cumulative volumes with different conductivity values in the calibration period 2011-2015.

Figure 5.13 Head aquifer with different conductivity values in the calibration period 2011-2015.

5.5 Channel routing

Discharge routing is computed according to the variable parameter Muskingum-Cunge-Todini method (Todini, 2007), applied to every cell of the computation domain with length Δx .

The outflow $O_{t+\Delta t}$ from a reach segment of length Δx is given by a linear combination of variable coefficients and the inflow, I , and outflow at time t and $t+\Delta t$.

$$O_{t+\Delta t} = C_1 * I_{t+\Delta t} + C_2 * I_t + C_3 * O_t + C_4 * Q_l \quad \text{Eq.(5.17)}$$

where Q_l is lateral inflow.

$$C_1 = \frac{-1 + C_{t+\Delta t}^* + D_{t+\Delta t}^*}{1 + C_{t+\Delta t}^* + D_{t+\Delta t}^*} \quad \text{Eq.(5.18)}$$

$$C_2 = \frac{1 + C_t^* - D_t^*}{1 + C_{t+\Delta t}^* + D_{t+\Delta t}^*} * \frac{C_{t+\Delta t}^*}{C_t^*} \quad \text{Eq.(5.19)}$$

The coefficients expressed in terms of corrected Courant C and Reynolds D^* numbers are given by the following expressions:

$$C_3 = \frac{1 - C_t^* + D_t^*}{1 + C_{t+\Delta t}^* + D_{t+\Delta t}^*} * \frac{C_{t+\Delta t}^*}{C_t^*} \quad \text{Eq.(5.20)}$$

$$C_4 = \frac{2 * C_{t+\Delta t}^*}{1 + C_{t+\Delta t}^* + D_{t+\Delta t}^*} \quad \text{Eq.(5.21)}$$

with

$$C_t^* = \frac{c_t}{\beta_t} * \frac{\Delta_t}{\Delta_X} \quad \text{Eq.(5.22)}$$

$$C_{t+\Delta t}^* = \frac{c_{t+\Delta t}}{\beta_{t+\Delta t}} * \frac{\Delta_t}{\Delta_X} \quad \text{Eq.(5.23)}$$

$$D_t^* = \frac{Q_t}{\beta_t * B * S_0 * c_t * \Delta_X} \quad \text{Eq.(5.24)}$$

$$D_{t+\Delta t}^* = \frac{Q_{t+\Delta t}}{\beta_{t+\Delta t} * B * S_0 * c_{t+\Delta t} * \Delta_X} \quad \text{Eq.(5.25)}$$

where c is the wave celerity, B is channel top width, S_0 is reach bed slope, and $\beta = \frac{c \cdot A}{Q}$ a dimensionless correcting factor.

A first guess estimate $\hat{O}_{t+\Delta t}$ for the outflow $O_{t+\Delta t}$ at time $t+\Delta t$ is initially computed as:

$$\hat{O}_{t+\Delta t} = O_t * (I_{t+\Delta t} - I_t) \quad \text{Eq.(5.26)}$$

where O_t is outflow a time t , $I_{t+\Delta t}$ and I_t are inflow at time $t+\Delta t$, and t , respectively.

Then the reference discharge is computed at time t , and $t+\Delta t$ as:

$$Q_t = \frac{I_t + O_t}{2} \quad \text{Eq.(5.27)}$$

$$Q_{t+\Delta t} = \frac{I_{t+\Delta t} + \hat{O}_{t+\Delta t}}{2} \quad \text{Eq.(5.28)}$$

and the reference water levels, y (normal depth), can be derived by means of a Newton-Raphson approach from the following implicit equations:

$$y_t = y[Q_t, n, S_0] \quad \text{Eq.(5.29)}$$

$$y_{t+\Delta t} = y[Q_{t+\Delta t}, n, S_0] \quad \text{Eq.(5.30)}$$

where n is Manning roughness coefficient, and S_0 is bed slope.

Using the reference discharge and water level it is then possible to estimate all the other quantities at times t and $t+\Delta t$.

The celerity:

$$c_t = c[Q_t, y_t, n, S_0] \quad \text{Eq.(5.31)}$$

$$c_{t+\Delta t} = c[Q_{t+\Delta t}, y_{t+\Delta t}, n, S_0] \quad \text{Eq.(5.32)}$$

the actual expressions for the celerity valid for triangular, rectangular and trapezoidal cross sections.

The correcting factor, β :

$$\beta_t = \frac{c_t * A_t}{Q_t} \quad \text{Eq.(5.33)}$$

$$\beta_{t+\Delta t} = \frac{c_{t+\Delta t} * A_{t+\Delta t}}{Q_{t+\Delta t}} \quad \text{Eq.(5.34)}$$

The corrected Courant numbers, and cell Reynolds numbers, from Equations 9-6 ÷ 9-9, and the weight coefficients, C_1 ÷ C_4 , from Equations 5.18 ÷ 5.21. The outflow is finally computed with Equation 5.19.

5.5.1 Results and comments

The results from all previously conducted simulations indicate a systematic early prediction of flow peaks by the model. To correct this, it is necessary to adjust the discharge routing by modifying the Manning coefficient n (identified in the code as the Strickler coefficient $k_S = \frac{1}{n}$) and the width of the hydrographic network branches. This adjustment aims to delay the flow and synchronize it with the observed flood peaks. Although this operation falls fully within the scope of sensitivity analysis, it slightly deviates from previous procedures as it involves direct comparison with observed flows rather than the standard simulation. Furthermore, due to the nature of the process, the calculation of aggregated values was not necessary, as the operation focuses solely on the timing of the flood peaks rather than

their actual values. Additionally, given the deterministic effect of the process, simulations were conducted only up to December 31, 2011, to save time for subsequent operations.

Other parameters that can be modified are those related to the slopes of the hydrological basin. By increasing the threshold below which the above-described method is applied and its related magnitude, the maximum flood peak and how the event is absorbed by the hydrological system are affected.

The above graphs show the model's behavior during the annual flood peak for the six measurement stations considered. Three different functions are reported: the observed flow rates, the standard simulation (the same used as a reference in the other sections of the chapter), and the "adjusted simulation," which is the result of the following configuration (for more detail consult the [user guide manual](#)) :

- Hillslope:
 - Threshold = 3,000,000
 - Width = 1500
- Hydrographic network:

Table 5.17 Properties of the hydrological channel

THRESHOLD [m ²]	WIDTH [m]	Ks [m ^{1/3} /s]
1000000	50	5
5000000	100	7.5
10000000	200	10
20000000	350	12.5
100000000	450	17.5
1000000000	600	22.5
10000000000	2000	25
100000000000	3500	27.5

The effect of this configuration is a delay in the flood peak of the standard simulation, along with a decrease in terms of maximum flow rate and a distribution of the total volume over several days, a behavior more like the observed flow rates.

Figure 5.14 Simulated and observed discharge with different configurations in the 2011 annual peak period.

CHAPTER 6

FEST CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION

In this chapter, we utilize the knowledge acquired in the previous chapter to find the best parameters configuration that allows the model to accurately replicate the actual hydrological regime of the Po River across the six measurement stations previously listed. The calibration period spans from January 1, 2011, to December 31, 2015.

Unlike the sensitivity analysis, in this case, the flows estimated by the model are directly compared with the observed flows using various error statistics. The first two are the same as those used in the previous chapter: the average $\Delta\%$ of annual peak flows and the sum of the $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volumes, both calculated for each section and referring to the observed flows. Additionally, two other error indices are used:

- **Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE):** the root mean square error divided by the mean value of the observed data. This variant is used because the flow values increase downstream, necessitating a statistic that is not influenced by the absolute value of the measurements. The formula used is as follows:

$$NRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}}{\bar{y}} \quad \text{Eq.(6.1)}$$

with

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad \text{Eq.(6.2)}$$

- **Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE):** values range from negative infinity to 1, with 0 being the reference value, as it represents the result that would be obtained by replacing the simulated values with the mean of the observations. The formula is as follows:

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad \text{Eq.(6.3)}$$

These last two error statistics are calculated for each measurement station and then aggregated into a single value by calculating the mean. In this way, the performance of each parameter set considered is compared using four different aggregated statistics, providing an overview of the simulated flows.

6.1 Calibration

Starting from the configuration illustrated in the Channel Routing section, the following values are then assigned:

- Aquifer Conductivity: 10^5
- Permeability Scale Factor: 0.05

Table 6.1 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters

MEASURE STATION	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
SPESSA PO	84%	95%	65%	83%	96%
PIACENZA	95%	-20%	-37%	-33%	-13%
CREMONA	65%	-27%	-32%	-33%	-21%
BORETTO	83%	-24%	-41%	-36%	-16%
BORGOFORTE	96%	-21%	-33%	-32%	-11%
PONTELAGOSCURO	82%	-23%	-36%	-27%	-20%

Table 6.2 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume, NRMSE and NSE for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters

MEASURE STATION	$\Delta\%$	NRMSE	NSE
SPESSA PO	-14%	0.6515	0.4947
PIACENZA	2%	0.6041	0.5284
CREMONA	0%	0.5064	0.5899
BORETTO	-7%	0.5455	0.5861
BORGOFORTE	-1%	0.5000	0.5929
PONTELAGOSCURO	-2%	0.4916	0.5926

The aggregated values for both the chosen simulation and the standard simulation are reported, relative to the observed values. This comparison allows for a better understanding of the extent of performance improvements achieved during the calibration phase.

Table 6.3 Aggregated value for the simulation with the final set of parameters and the standard simulation

AGGREGATED VALUE	FINAL	STANDARD
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	-4%	149%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	22% ²	66% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	-22%	6%
NRMSE MEAN	0.5499	1.1687
NSE MEAN	0.5641	-0.98

Figure 6.1 Simulated discharge with the final set of parameters in 2014.

Figure 6.2 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the calibration period 2011-2015.

The importance of cyclostationary mean values lies in their ability to capture periodic patterns in hydrological data, which is crucial for understanding seasonal variations and improving model accuracy. According to literature (Zhang et al, 2022), cyclostationarity in hydrological processes allows for a more nuanced analysis of data that exhibits regular, repeating patterns over time.

The following graph depicts the seasonal variations in water flow, highlighting two distinct peak periods in spring and autumn. These peaks are followed by decreases in water flow during winter and summer. This pattern reflects the typical hydrological cycle in the region, influenced by seasonal rainfall and temperature changes. The spring peak is usually driven by melting snow and increased rainfall, while the autumn peak results from post-summer precipitation. Conversely, the lower flows in winter are due to frozen ground conditions and reduced precipitation, while summer reductions are attributable to higher evapotranspiration rates.

Figure 6.3 Waterflow cyclostationary observed and simulated mean in Pontelagoscuro during the calibration period 2011-2015.

6.2 Validation

The validation of the model extends the temporal horizon to December 31, 2020. Evaluating the model's performance over this period is crucial for assessing its robustness and reliability.

The validation includes various performance indicators and graphical representations to ensure a comprehensive evaluation.

Table 6.4 $\Delta\%$ of waterflow annual peak for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the period 2016-2020

MEASURE STATION	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
SPESSA PO	25%	36%	-10%	0%	-1%
PIACENZA	43%	5%	-7%	3%	11%
CREMONA	58%	5%	1%	-3%	12%
BORETTO	58%	9%	5%	5%	16%
BORGOFORTE	69%	13%	11%	6%	33%
PONTELAGOSCURO	56%	18%	12%	19%	37%

Table 6.5 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume, NRMSE and NSE for each measure station for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the validation period 2011-2020

MEASURE STATION	$\Delta\%$	NRMSE	NSE
SPESSA PO	5%	0.5626	0.5120
PIACENZA	11%	0.5757	0.5456
CREMONA	6%	0.4742	0.6090
BORETTO	1%	0.4870	0.6122
BORGOFORTE	5%	0.4568	0.6059
PONTELAGOSCURO	7%	0.4462	0.5935

Table 6.6 Aggregated value for the simulation with the final set of parameters for the calibration and validation period

AGGREGATED VALUE	CALIBRATION	VALIDATION
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	-4%	8%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	22% ²	14% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	-22%	35%
NRMSE MEAN	0.5499	0.5004
NSE MEAN	0.5641	0.5797

Figure 6.4 Simulated discharge with the final set of parameters in 2017.

Figure 6.5 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the validation period 2011-2020.

Figure 6.6 Waterflow cyclostationary observed and simulated mean in Pontelagoscuro during the validation period 2011-2020.

By incorporating these graphical analyses and the table with aggregated values, the validation section aims to provide a detailed and clear evaluation of the model's performance, highlighting both its strengths and areas for improvement. This comprehensive approach ensures that the model can be reliably used for future predictions and management of the Po River Basin's water resources. The comparison of aggregated values between calibration and validation phases demonstrates that there are no significant changes in performance, underscoring the model's reliability.

CHAPTER 7

EXPLORING IRRIGATION SCENARIOS

In this chapter, various scenarios are explored by modifying the irrigation practices within the model. To better understand the effect of irrigation deactivation, the measurement stations of Isola Sant'Antonio and Ponte della Becca are considered. Their characteristics are detailed in Table 7.1.

Table 7.1 New location of different sections of Po River considered for the comparison.

SECTION	REGION	ELEVATION	LONG.	LAT.
Isola Sant'Antonio	Piemonte	76	8.8483	45.0447
Ponte della Becca	Lombardia	73	9.2263.	45.1402

Having calibrated and validated the model on the previous six measurement stations, it is possible to integrate these two new stations. Their inclusion is crucial for understanding the irrigation effect along the Ticino River on the Po River regime. Figure 7.1 illustrates the new configuration:

- Isola Sant'Antonio Station: located before the confluence of the Ticino with the Po.
- Ponte della Becca Station: situated at the confluence.
- Spessa Po Station: positioned just after the confluence.
- Piacenza Station: located downstream from the confluence of both the Ticino and other minor tributaries less used for irrigation.

7.1 Comparison with No Irrigation Simulation

The irrigation period in the model spans from 15th April to 15th September. In the subsequent simulation, the model is configured similarly to the previous setup but without activating the agricultural irrigation components. This adjustment is expected to lead to increased river flows, reduced evapotranspiration, and higher aquifer levels, especially during the drier months.

- **Increased River Flows:** without the diversion of water for agricultural purposes, more water remains in the river channels, resulting in higher flow rates.
- **Reduced Evapotranspiration:** the absence of irrigation decreases water availability for crops, thereby reducing the overall evapotranspiration rates.
- **Reduced level of aquifer:** the absence of irrigation reduces water being drawn from the rivers to the fields, resulting in a notable decrease in aquifer height.

Typically, irrigation practices increase groundwater levels as water infiltrates from irrigated fields, raising the aquifer height. The following graphs and tables will be included to illustrate these changes:

Table 7.2 Aggregated value for the final simulation with and without irrigation in the validation period 2011-2020.

AGGREGATED VALUE	FINAL SIMULATION	NO IRRIGATION
ANNUAL PEAK MEAN	8%	10%
ANNUAL PEAK VARIANCE	14% ²	14% ²
CUMULATIVE VOLUME SUM	35%	64%
NRMSE MEAN	0.5004	0.5351
NSE MEAN	0.5797	0.5189

Table 7.3 Annual $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume between the simulations with and without the irrigation

	ISOLA SANT'ANTONIO	PONTE BECCA	SPESSA PO	PIACENZA	CREMONA	BORETTO	BORGIO	PONTE.
2011	3.99%	12.37%	8.45%	4.78%	6.83%	6.61%	5.47%	5.78%
2012	5.64%	13.06%	8.43%	4.35%	6.26%	6.08%	4.90%	5.10%
2013	4.84%	11.26%	7.86%	3.93%	6.05%	5.83%	4.75%	5.18%
2014	4.61%	9.32%	6.71%	2.85%	4.70%	4.55%	3.72%	4.10%
2015	4.87%	10.93%	7.48%	3.49%	5.64%	5.45%	4.42%	4.79%
2016	4.76%	9.53%	6.78%	2.74%	4.67%	4.52%	3.64%	4.03%
2017	5.08%	11.40%	7.55%	3.33%	5.50%	5.31%	4.28%	4.62%
2018	4.53%	8.90%	6.43%	2.60%	4.58%	4.44%	3.61%	4.03%
2019	4.87%	10.78%	7.30%	3.11%	5.35%	5.10%	4.14%	4.49%

2020	4.72%	9.03%	6.49%	2.55%	4.59%	4.39%	3.63%	4.04%
AVG	4.79%	10.66%	7.35%	3.37%	5.42%	5.23%	4.25%	4.62%

Table 7.4 $\Delta\%$ of cumulative volume during the irrigation period between the simulations with and without the irrigation

	ISOLA SANT'ANTONIO	PONTE BECCA	SPESSA PO	PIACENZA	CREMONA	BORETTO	BORGO.	PONTE.
2011	11.86%	39.38%	25.19%	15.06%	21.07%	20.28%	16.60%	17.19%
2012	11.51%	30.42%	20.39%	11.96%	16.76%	16.40%	13.50%	13.97%
2013	8.96%	18.69%	14.69%	8.00%	12.26%	12.14%	10.05%	11.28%
2014	10.73%	22.79%	17.25%	8.28%	13.18%	12.74%	10.88%	12.04%
2015	10.12%	24.06%	16.79%	9.07%	14.26%	13.96%	11.98%	12.53%
2016	13.53%	26.94%	18.88%	9.07%	14.04%	13.66%	11.15%	11.98%
2017	11.31%	28.72%	18.21%	8.72%	13.69%	13.40%	11.22%	11.80%
2018	8.26%	17.79%	13.91%	7.61%	12.41%	12.01%	10.61%	11.66%
2019	10.97%	26.67%	19.16%	9.53%	15.88%	14.67%	12.77%	13.55%
2020	10.08%	21.68%	16.18%	8.24%	13.60%	12.83%	11.69%	12.59%
AVG	10.73%	25.71%	18.07%	9.55%	14.71%	14.21%	12.05%	12.86%

Figure 7.1 Waterflow cyclostationary simulated means with and without irrigation in Pontelagoscuro during the validation period 2011-2020.

Figure 7.2 Cumulative volumes with the final set of parameters in the validation period 2011-2020.

Figure 7.3 Evapotranspiration cyclostationary simulated means with and without irrigation during the validation period 2011-2020.

Figure 7.4 Head of aquifer compared with the cumulated discharge volume of the irrigation.

By comparing these results with those from the standard simulation that includes agricultural irrigation, we can clearly observe the impacts of irrigation on the hydrological cycle. From Tables 7.3 and 7.4, it can be calculated that, on average, annual cumulative volumes decrease by 5.71% due to irrigation. This value increases to 15.00% when considering only the irrigation period from April 15 to September 15.

The tables also illustrate the influence of irrigation along the Ticino River on the Po River's flow rates. Even by analyzing the average percentage changes, it is evident that these changes are more than double at the Ponte della Becca station compared to those at Isola Sant'Antonio. This is because, as mentioned earlier, the Ticino River is extensively used for agriculture on both the Lombardy and Piedmont sides, irrigating areas such as Novara, known for rice production.

The results obtained are consistent with reality and highlight the importance of selecting analysis points along the river. Identifying points upstream, downstream, and at the confluences of major tributaries is crucial for representing the most general possible reality. The behavior at the Piacenza section is equally consistent, with percentage changes even lower than those at Isola Sant'Antonio. This is because Piacenza is located downstream from the

confluence of the Ticino and other less exploited rivers for irrigation, thus attenuating the irrigation effect.

From Figure 7.4, the difference in aquifer height between the two scenarios can be observed. The overlay with the cumulative volume of irrigation helps identify irrigation periods. In the no-irrigation scenario, the aquifer systematically lowers, while in the irrigation scenario, the decline is much less pronounced, increasing the divergence in aquifer height over time. This occurs because the diverted water is partially absorbed by plants, partially evaporates (increasing evapotranspiration), and partially infiltrates into the aquifer, raising its average level across the basin. Agricultural efficiency aims to minimize these latter two phenomena without altering the amount of water required for plant growth.

7.2 Future development

Possible future developments include varying the irrigation windows and modifying the allocation rates. Additionally, it would be beneficial to conduct analyses on the impact of modifying the water concession system for irrigation during particularly dry years, such as 2022. These adjustments can help in optimizing water usage and ensuring the sustainability of water resources in the region. By exploring different irrigation schedules, water concession rates, and emergency measures for drought conditions, it is possible to identify strategies that minimize water stress while maintaining agricultural productivity.

For example, different irrigation schedules could take advantage of temperature increases to extend the irrigation window while providing the option to irrigate in shifts, thereby reducing peak water demand, especially during summer.

Furthermore, it would be interesting to consider collaborations with the consortia that manage irrigation. Their expertise and knowledge can significantly contribute to the creation of plausible irrigation scenarios, aiding in the better management of irrigation resources while preserving the agricultural heritage of the region. Such collaborations can foster the development of more effective and sustainable water management practices, ensuring both agricultural productivity and resource conservation.

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSIONS

This thesis has focused on assessing the impact of agricultural irrigation on the hydrological regime of the Po River Basin using the FEST (Flash Flood Event-based Simulation Technique) hydrological model. The main objectives were to understand the effects of irrigation practices on river flows, evapotranspiration rates, and aquifer levels, and to explore scenarios that can help optimize water resource management.

The study began with a comprehensive analysis of the Po River Basin, including its meteorological and soil parameters. MERIDA historical data from 2011 to 2020 has been used for the calibration and validation of the FEST model. The model's reliability was demonstrated through simulations that accurately captured river discharges and cumulative water volumes. A significant portion of the work involved detailed research on the main water diversions of the major tributaries of the Po River. For each tributary, the major diversions were identified, including their irrigated areas and the allocated water flow rates. This extensive research required reviewing the bibliographic resources available on the websites of the irrigation consortia. This was undoubtedly the most time-consuming part of the study, providing crucial data for accurately modeling the water distribution and usage within the basin.

The simulations revealed that irrigation significantly affects the hydrological cycle. Irrigation practices lead to a reduction in river flows and aquifer levels while increasing evapotranspiration rates. This is particularly noticeable during the irrigation period from April to September. A scenario without agricultural irrigation showed increased river flows and higher aquifer levels, especially during dry months. The absence of irrigation decreased water availability for crops, reducing overall evapotranspiration.

From Tables 7.3 and 7.4, it was calculated that irrigation reduces the annual cumulative volumes by an average of 5.71%, a figure that increases to 15.00% considering only the irrigation period from 15th April to 15th September. This period also sees increased

evapotranspiration and a decrease in aquifer height throughout the year, as illustrated in Figure 7.3 and 7.4.

The findings underscore the significant influence of agricultural irrigation on the region's water resources. Effective management practices must consider these impacts to balance agricultural needs with the sustainability of water resources. Future research should explore varying irrigation windows and modifying water allocation rates. Additionally, analyzing the impacts of changing the water concession system during particularly dry years, such as 2022, could provide insights for better water resource management. Collaborations with irrigation consortia could further refine these scenarios, leveraging their expertise to create plausible irrigation management strategies.

In conclusion, this thesis provides a detailed analysis of the hydrological dynamics of the Po River Basin under different irrigation scenarios. The insights gained are vital for developing sustainable water management practices that can adapt to the challenges posed by climate change and ensure the long-term viability of agricultural productivity in the region.

Bibliography

- [1] **Adornado Yoshida**; GIS-based watershed analysis and surface runoff estimation using curve number value [Rapporto]. - Ibaraki, Japan : Journal of Environmental Hydrology, 2010.
- [2] **Antonaci M**; The Light Canvas [Online]. - 29 April 2016. - <https://www.thelightcanvas.com/il-canale-cavour-un-colosso-dellingegneria-idraulica/>.
- [3] **Arnold JG, Allen PM, Bernhardt G** (1993) A comprehensive surface-groundwater flow model. J Hydrol 142:47–69
- [4] **Bozzola M, and Swanson T**. Policy implications of climate variability on agriculture: Water management in the Po River basin, Italy, Environmental Science & Policy, Volume 43, 2014, Pages 26-38, ISSN 1462-9011 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2013.12.002>.
- [5] **Camporese M, Paniconi C, Putti M, Orlandini S** (2010) Surface-subsurface flow modeling with path-based runoff routing, boundary condition-based coupling, and assimilation of multisource observation data. Water Resour Res 46, W02512. doi:10.1029/2008WR007536
- [6] **Consorzio Bonifica Muzza Bassa Lodigiana**; www.muzza.it [Online]. - <https://www.muzza.it/irrigazione.php>.
- [7] **Consorzio del Ticino**; Ricerca sul Deflusso Minimo Vitale del fiume Ticino dalla diga della Miorina alla confluenza col il Po [Libro]. - Milano : Hydrodata S.p.A, 1999.
- [8] **Consorzio dell'Adda**; [Online] // addaconsorzio.it/. - 1 Maggio 1990. - <https://www.addaconsorzio.it/>.
- [9] **Consorzio di bonifica Chiese**; Piano comprensionale di bonifica, di irrigazione e di tutela del territorio rurale [Rapporto]. - 2018.
- [10] **Consorzio di Bonifica della Media Pianura Bergamasca**; www.cbbg.it [Online]. - <https://www.cbbg.it/irrigazioni/informazioni-general/impianti/>.
- [11] **Consorzio di bonifica Territori sul Mincio**; Piano comprensionale di bonifica, di irrigazione e di tutela del territorio rurale [Rapporto]. - 2018.
- [12] **Core Writing Team: Pachauri R.K. and Reisinger A.**; Climate Change 2007: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the

- Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Libro] / a cura di IPCC. - Geneva, Switzerland : [s.n.], 2007.
- [13] **Coulon-Leroy Cécile [et al.]**; Fuzzy Modeling of a Composite Agronomical Feature Using FisPro: The Case of Vine Vigor [Rapporto].
- [14] **Denti Ballarin , A**; Rapporto sullo stato delle conoscenze scientifiche su impatti, vulnerabilità ed adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici in Italia [Libro]. - 9788887728095.
- [15] **Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering**; Reference Manual [Rapporto]. - [s.l.] : Politecnico di Milano.
- [16] **Fiseha BM, Setegn SG, Melesse AM, Voli E, Fiori A** (2014) Impact of climate change on the hydrology of Upper Tiber river basin using bias corrected regional climate model. *Water resources management* 28: 1327-1343. Doi:10.1007/s11269-014-0546-x
- [17] **Formetta G; Tootle G; Therrell M**. Regional Reconstruction of Po River Basin (Italy) Streamflow []. - 23065338.
- [18] **Franés F; Vélez JI; Vélez JJ**; Split-parameter structure for the automatic calibration of distributed hydrological models [Journal] // *Journal of Hydrology*. - 2007. - p. 226-240.
- [19] **Franzoni F**. EstSesia.it [Online]. - 28 Agosto 2012. - <https://web.archive.org/web/20070706102314/http://www.estsesia.it/comprensorio/rete.html>.
- [20] **Gandolfi C**. Acqua e irrigazione per nutrire il pianeta. La realtà della Pianura Padana Lombarda [Rapporto] / Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali, Università degli Studi di Milano. - Milano : [s.n.], 2017.
- [21] **Graham DN, Butts MB** (2005) Flexible, integrated watershed modelling with MIKE SHE. In *Watershed Models*, Eds. VP Singh & DK Frevert, pp 245-272, CRC Press
- [22] **Istituto nazionale di economia agraria (a cura di Zucaro R. e Trione S.)** Rapporto sullo stato dell'irrigazione in Piemonte [Rapporto]. - Roma : INEA, 2011.
- [23] **I Consorzi di bonifica della Lombardia** Appunto per l'Audizione presso la 9° Commissione permanente Agricoltura e produzione agroalimentare del Senato della Repubblica [Online]. - 2019. - https://www.senato.it/application/xmanager/projects/leg18/attachments/documento_evento_procedura_commissione/files/000/001/459/ANBI_Lombardia_Nota_Commissione_Agricoltura_del_Senato-Consorzi_Lombardi_Agricoltura_Acqua_Clima.pdf.
- [24] **McDonald M; Harbaugh A**; Modular Three-Dimensional Finite Difference Ground-Water Flow Model. In: *Techniques of Water-Resources Investigations* [].
- [25] **Racchetti E, Salmaso F, Pinardi M, Quadroni S, Soana E, Sacchi E, Severini E, Celico F, Viaroli P, Bartoli M**. Is Flood Irrigation a Potential

-
- Driver of River-Groundwater Interactions and Diffuse Nitrate Pollution in Agricultural Watersheds? *Water*. 2019; 11(11):2304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11112304>
- [26] **Ravazzani G. [et al.]** An integrated Hydrological Model for Assessing Climate Change Impacts on Water Resources of the Upper Po River Basin [Libro]. - 2015. - Vol. *Water Resources Management* : 29(4) : p. 1193-1215.
- [27] **Ravazzani G., Rametta D. e Mancini M.** Macroscopic Cellular Automata for groundwater modelling: a first approach [Rapporto]. - 2011.
- [28] **Ravazzani Mancini, Giudici, Amadio** Effect of soil moisture parametrization on real-time flood forecasting system based on rainfall thresholds [Rapporto]. - Wallingford, UK : IAHS Press, 2007.
- [29] **Ravelli A.** Brescia Genealogia [Online]. - 8 Gennaio 2020. - <https://bresciagenealogia.wordpress.com/2020/01/08/le-seriole-dellalta-pianura-bresciana>.
- [30] **Senatore A, Mendicino G, Smiatek G, Kunstmann H.** Regional climate change projections and hydrological impact analysis for a Mediterranean basin in Southern Italy, *Journal of Hydrology*, Volume 399, Issues 1–2, 2011, Pages 70-92, ISSN 0022-1694, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2010.12.035>
- [31] **SCS** , Soil Conservation Services [Sezione di libro] // *National Engineering Handbook* / aut. libro USDA. - Washington DC : [s.n.], 1985.
- [32] **Soulis Valiantzas** SCS-CN parameter determination using rainfall-runoff data in heterogeneous watersheds - The two CN system approach [Rapporto]. - *Sci : Hydrological Earth System*, 2012. - p. 1001-1015.
- [33] **Strzepek K. [et al.]** Climate variability and change: A basin scale indicator approach to understanding the risk to water resources development and management [Rapporto]. - Washington : The World Bank, 2011.
- [34] **Todini E.** A mass conservative and water storage consistent variable parameter Muskingum-Cunge approach [Libro]. - [s.l.] : *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci*, 2007. - p. 1645–1659.
- [35] **Ungaro F., Calzolari C. e Busoni E.** Development of pedotransfer functions using a group method of data handling for the soil of the Pianura Padano-Veneta region of North Italy: water retention properties [Libro]. - [s.l.] : *Geoderma*, 2005. - Vol. 124 : p. 293-317.

